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Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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1 Introduction

ECOBULK, through large scale demonstrations, aims to contribute to “closing the loop” of composite products in the automotive, furniture and building sectors by promoting greater re-use, upgrade, refurbishment and recycle of products, parts, and materials. The demonstration in the automotive sector involves the development of internal car parts made with closed-loop recycled plastics. The internal car part selected for demonstration purposes was a central console fascia for Dacia Lodge, which is composed of a front side and a back side, both made of plastic materials. Different fascia prototypes were developed in the project, which were based on different plastic materials (ABS, PLA and PP) and incorporated various recycled plastic contents in the back side. Regarding the furniture, the demonstration selected for this s-LCA is a functional unit based on a set of furniture to furnish a complete room made of wood containing the adhesives developed during the project and comparing it to the same case but built using only common wood. Finally, for the construction sector, the demonstrator selected is composed by a value chain around the material developed by Conenor during the project.

The aim of this report is to evaluate the potential social impacts and benefits of the new prototypes (e.g. in the automotive sector, fascia prototypes made with closed-loop recycled plastics). To this end, a social impact assessment was conducted to evaluate and compare the different product baselines.

2 Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) methodology

Within the ECOBULK project, S-LCA will be applied to evaluate the social impacts of the demonstrators under development in three sectors (automotive, construction and furniture) in order to identify ways of improvements of the solutions developed and, when relevant, to compare the benefits of different business models.

This task is parallel to the Life Cycle Costing assessment and the Environment life cycle assessment, which are developed in the deliverable D7.2.

2.1 UNEP guidelines for S-LCA

UNEP released in 2009 some guidelines¹ that laid the foundation to the methodological and technical aspects to evaluate the social and socio-economic impacts, positive and negative, of a product through its life cycle.

S-LCA is in line with ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards for Life Cycle Assessment, and it can be applied by itself or combined with LCA and or LCC.

Thus it can be carried out in four phases: (i) goal and scope definition, (ii) life cycle inventory, (iii) impact assessment, and (iv) interpretation of results.

¹ Andrews, E. S., Barthel, L.-P., Beck, T., Benoit, C., Ciroth, A., Cucuzella, C., Gensch, C.-O., Hérbert, J., Lesage, P., Manhart, A., Mazeau, P., Mazijn, B., Methot, A.-L., Moberg, A., Norris, G., Parent, J., Prakash, S., Reveret, J.-P., Spillemaeckers, S., Ugaya, C. M. L., Valdivia, S., Weidema, B. (2009): UNEP/SETAC Life Cycle Initiative: Guidelines for social life cycle assessment of products, 2009. http://www.unep.fr/shared/publications/pdf/DTIx1164xPA-guidelines_sLCA.pdf

Figure 1: LCA phases according to ISO 14040:2006

Like environmental LCA, social LCA should fulfil the same uses as those listed in ISO 14044 which are: i) help to raise awareness of the social problems linked to the existence of product chains, ii) identify critical points and margins for improvement, iii) enable the development of alternative scenarios.

But although S-LCA follows the framework of ISO 14040, some methodological aspects differ. The UNEP guidelines provide a methodology for developing life cycle inventories by considering the perspectives of different stakeholders: workers, local communities, value chain actors, customers, and consumers. These guidelines consider six main impact categories: human rights, health and safety, governance, working conditions, socio-economic impacts and cultural heritage.

Figure 2: The assessment reference framework. (Source: UNEP/SETAC, Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products, (2009))

2.1.1 Goal of the analysis

A Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) is an assessment technique that aims to assess the potential positive and negatives social and socio-economic impacts of products (UNEP, 2009) along their whole life cycle: extraction and processing of raw materials, manufacturing, distribution, use, and end of life.

S-LCA provides information on social aspects for decision making, encourage dialogue between stakeholders and along the value chain in order to improve performance of organizations and ultimately the well-being of stakeholders.

Among the main stakeholders, categories are as follows:

The first step of a S-LCA is to define the goals and the scopes of the studies by describing the studies and their purposes. The definition of the goal has to be clearly specified to ensure the study will fulfil the intended application.

And finally the study needs to be framed within boundaries that will define which the limits of the flows that will be taken into account.

In this project, the goal, scope and system boundaries will be aligned on the choices made in the deliverable D7.2 to carry out LCA and LCC.

2.1.2 Inventory analysis

The inventory analysis of a S-LCA is the phase where data are collected, the system are modelled and results of the inventory are obtained (UNEP, 2009). UNEP suggests a plan for conducting the inventory analysis of the S-LCA. Different steps of the life cycle inventory are suggest as follows.

- Data collection
- Preparing for main data collection
- Main data collection
- Data needed for impact assessment
- Validation of data
- Relating data to functional unit and unit process
- Refining the system boundary
- Data aggregation

The data collection is separated in two steps. The first one is the localisation of the unit processes and the determination of the organizations who are involved for data that needs to be collected. For data that may be collected, the determination of activities who are variable is necessary. The second step of the data collection is to find hotspots of the product's life cycle, which is to say what the mains inputs to the life cycle of the product are.

The preparation of the main data collection can be conducted by literature review, web research or site specific data collection via questionnaire or social audits.

Data validation need to follow some criteria explained below:

- Validity (consistency between data collected and information intended)
- Relevance (comparison of similar data)
- Measurement methods (appropriate method for collected data)
- Completeness (availability of data)
- Accessibility / Documentation (information about data used)
- Uncertainty (adequate number of observation)

A sensitive analysis should be conducted to revise the initial system boundary, in accordance with the cut-off criteria established in the definition of the scope. (ISO 14044, 2006).

2.1.3 Impact assessment

In this phase, the idea is to provide a combination of:

- aggregating some inventory data within social subcategories and categories; and
- making use of additional information, such as internationally accepted levels of minimum performance, to help understand the magnitude and the significance of the data collected in the inventory phase.

2.1.4 Social life cycle interpretation

In this final step, the social footprint of the new products was analysed to determine their social hotspots and identify possibilities for improvement.

These results were compared with those of current equivalent products to determine the potential social benefits that can be derived from the project.

The conclusions and recommendations will enlighten partners on social aspects important to take into account in the design process.

2.2 Handbook for PSIA

In 2018, companies in the Roundtable for Product Social Metrics produced a handbook for Product Social Impact Assessment (PSIA)². This book describes a consensus-based methodology to assess positive and negative social impacts of products and services on four stakeholder groups: workers, local communities, small-scale entrepreneurs and users.

Different steps of this method are listed below:

- Preparation phase
- Defining goal and scope
- Identifying hotspots
- Assessing social impact on workers, small-scale entrepreneurs and local communities
- Assessing social impact on users
- Interpreting the results

The Roundtable for Product Social Metrics explains the main difference between UNEP/SETAC Guidelines and the handbook for Product Social Impact Assessment by saying: "A key difference with the UNEP/SETAC Guidelines is our strong focus on applicability and business relevance. This Roundtable was initiated because the companies recognised the need for a social impact assessment methodology that is relevant for business. The Roundtable focused on cases, shared learnings and experiences, to truly test the feasibility and practicability of the method." (Product Social Impact Assessment Handbook, 2018)

2.3 Social databases

S-LCA databases such as SHDB3 and PSILCA4 allow to automatize a great number of the S-LCA steps, especially those related to the S-LCIA phase, using generic data from national and international organizations. These databases are normally implemented in an LCA software (e.g., SimaPro, GaBi or openLCA) to facilitate and automatize their use.

² Goedkoop, M.J. Indrane, D.; de Beer, I.M.; Product Social Impact Assessment Handbook - 2018, Amersfoort, September 1st, 2018

³ SHDB – Social Hotspots Database: <http://www.socialhotspot.org>

⁴ PSILCA – Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment database: <https://psilca.net>

The method, social indicators and datasets of the SHDB, which was incorporated within SimaPro⁵ software, were used to tackle the development of the S-LCA study more effectively. The SHDB assesses 25 social sub-categories that can be grouped into 5 social categories. It also provides a weighted aggregation model that converts the values of impacts for each social subcategory into aggregated impact values for each social category, which in turn can be aggregated until arriving at a single global social impact indicator (the so-called Social Hotspot Index or SHI).

Figure 3. Main data components of the SHDB. *Source: adapted from Benoit et al. (2019).*

Figure 3 outlines the SHDB method followed herein to develop the S-LCA study of the target products. It includes the following steps and data components:

1) Information on supply chain composition and location

Knowledge on where the production activities are taking place is a major consideration for S-LCA because of the influence of societal, political and cultural differences on the potential social impacts (Benoit-Norris et al., 2012a, 2014; Benoit-Norris & Norris, 2015). S-LCA therefore requires to define the supply chain composition by describing how the production costs are distributed among country-specific sectors (CSS); i.e., how costs are allocated to each sector/country pair (e.g., Euros spent in plastics sector in Spain).

⁵ SimaPro: <https://simapro.com>

Takin as example, the automotive sector, a breakdown of the total production costs by CSS was developed from primary data provided by industry partner (MAIER) for each fascia model under study, considering Tier 1 level suppliers. The production costs were grouped into the following sectors in several countries (that were different depending on each raw material or component): chemicals and plastic materials, metal products, electricity, gas manufacture and distribution, motor vehicles and parts, transport, paper and wood products (only for packaging).

The SHDB incorporates a Global Input-Output model that provides information on the trade flows between the economic sectors of each country or region of the world (including 57 sectors in 140 regions/countries). The so-called GTAP (Global Trade Analysis Project) model was used to complete the definition of the supply chain composition for the target products by modelling how the economic amounts purchased from the CSS related to Tier 1 suppliers are contributed by other CSS (related to lower-Tier suppliers).

2) Information on the economic sector labour-intensity

Labour-intensity, expressed in terms of worker-hours, plays the role of what environmental LCA refers to as an 'elementary flow'; i.e., the basic or first-order 'intervention' by a production process that ultimately is linked to outcomes or impacts of interest. More generally, worker-hours are relevant because they represent evidence of the intensity of work required by each CSS directly related to production (Benoit-Norris et al., 2012a; Benoit-Norris & Norris, 2015).

The SHDB provides a worker-hours model that is based on average wage payments for each sector in each of the GTAP country/region. Thus, the SHDB was used to identify how many worker-hours are involved for each CSS involved in the supply chain of the target products, according to the economic demands from each CSS quantified in the previous step.

3) Information on social risks

The SHDB also provides information on social risks and opportunities by country and economic sector, including 160 social impact indicators for the CSS covered by the GTAP model. 25 impact subcategories (Figure 4) can thus be assessed by a number of indicators depending on the data context; sometimes only one indicator is available and relevant and sometimes several indicators are used for a specific social subcategory. The interpretation of data and the determination of risk levels (from low to very high) are most often performed through consideration of the range and distribution of values exhibited for the indicators across the full population of sectors and countries (Benoit-Norris et al., 2012a; Benoit-Norris & Norris, 2015).

The labour-intensity information for each CSS is used together with the social risk levels there to determine how many worker-hours are linked to the social risk level for a given social subcategory in each CSS.

 Labour rights & decent work	Wage	Poverty	Child labour
	Forced labour	Excessive working time	Freedom of association
 Health & safety	Migrant labour	Social benefits	Labour laws & conventions
	Discrimination		Unemployment
 Human rights	Occupational toxics & hazards		Injuries & fatalities
	Indigenous rights	Gender equity	High conflict zones
 Governance	Non-communicable diseases		Communicable diseases
	Legal system		Corruption
 Community	Access to drinking water	Access to sanitation	Children out of school
	Access to hospital beds		Smallholder vs commercial farms

Figure 4. Social categories and subcategories included in the S-LCA (using SHDB).

4) Social Hotspot Index (SHI)

The SHDB database includes information on 160 indicators covering 25 impact subcategories, 5 impact categories and 4 stakeholder groups: workers, local communities, value chain actors and society. Due to the large number of indicators and impact subcategories used and considering the specific evaluation for each country and economic sector, the S-LCA generates a large amount of data on social impacts that makes difficult to base decisions on. Therefore, to facilitate the understanding of the results and make sense of the social impact information available for each CSS, the SHI was created and it has been used in several studies (Benoit-Norris et al., 2012a, 2012b, 2014).

The SHI is an impact assessment method that combines the labour-intensity information with the social risk levels to express social risks (and opportunities) in terms of medium risk hours equivalent (Mrheq), by sector and country for the 5 social impact categories and the 25 social impact subcategories. The SHI is determined by first weighing the level of risk identified for each social impact subcategory, using weighting factors (as shown in Table 1). This weighting enlarges or reduces the number of workers-hours depending on the risk level, converting them into Mrheq. Thus, the same unit is used to calculate the impact on each social subcategory, so the impacts for different subcategories can be aggregated into single impact values for the corresponding social categories, which in turn can be aggregated into a single global social impact indicator, namely the so-called Social Hotspot Index or SHI. In the method applied herein, social

subcategories and categories are all weighted equally when adding them together (i.e., they are all given the same relevance).

Table 1. SHDB impact assessment method: weighting factors by default. Source: Benoit-Norris et al. (2019).

Risk level	Weighting factor
Very high risk (VH)	10
High risk (HR)	5
Medium risk (MR)	1
Low risk (LR)	0.1

The expression of social impacts in Mrheq was applied herein to aggregate the social impacts into a social footprint given by the SHI, which was calculated using the SHDB with the SimaPro software. Furthermore, it was helpful to identify target areas in the supply chain to improve social conditions; i.e., social hotspots or individual production activities/countries (identified by CSS) that contribute most to the risks (overall and/or by impact category or subcategory).

It should be noted that weighting factors in Table 1 are default values shown as an example, whilst the factors applied herein varied for each impact subcategory according to the number of social indicators used to assess such a subcategory. The weighting factors applied to each impact category, subcategory and social indicator are shown in Annex I.

2.4 S-LCA approach for the ECOBULK project

Withing the project, according to the data available, the SHDB database was used to assess the social performance of the automotive demonstrator, where the recommendations for the PSIA Handbook were followed for the furniture and the construction sector.

2.5 S-LCA projects and perspectives

Strength2Food is a 5-year EU-funded project that started in March 2016. This project will provide the EU and its Member States with evidence-based recommendations. Strength2Food will identify and implement strategies for upscaling: creating new and expanding existing markets for quality food products and fostering the development of an 'economy of quality'.

Strength2Food contains an assessment of the social, environmental and economic performance of 29 Food Quality Schemes (Bellassen et al., 2019)⁶.

⁶ Bellassen et al., 2019. Common method and indicators for sustainability assessment

The result for the example of PDO Comté cheese is reported below (see Figure 6).

Figure 5: Sustainability performance of PDO Comté cheese (Source: Bellassen et al., Common method and indicators for sustainability assessment, February 2019)

The Social Footprint Index Ltd., a fully independent non-profit organization, created the MyFootPrint platform for the purpose of informing and empowering consumers to build a more just and fair society. This tool is available on the web⁷.

Social Footprint - Product Social Identity (SFP) – an Italian organization – applies social certification for companies. Social Footprint Group provides a document⁸ containing the conditions to be met by an organisation in order to be able to apply for, obtain and maintain Social Footprint – Product Social Identity (SFP) certification. Ecopneus has obtained the Social Footprint certification (see Figure 7) for communicating the social and ethical identity of their products and services to the market in a transparent way.

⁷ <https://myfootprint.co/>

⁸ Social Footprint - Product Social Identity Rules for Certification document, 2015

Figure 6: Social Footprint certification for Ecopneus, 2014 (Source: Ecopneus)

Regarding the textile industry, the application Clear fashion provides information about social impact of clothes. Clear fashion uses data from website and CSR reports of companies, information supplied by clothing brands and information supplied by the user to determine a score with 4 themes: human, health, environment and animals (see Figure 8 for example).

Figure 7: Example of a scoring by Clear Fashion (Source: Clear Fashion)

Several commercial initiatives already exist, therefore the S-LCA carried out within ECOBULK will be put into perspective to identify possible business applications regarding the communication of social impacts of products.

2.6 S-LCA for the three sectors

2.6.1 S-LCA : Automotive sector

2.6.1.1 S-LCA : Automotive prototype

Prototypes of the internal car parts to be manufactured, demonstrated and subject to assessment in WP7 are the car central console panel (car fascia) developed by MAIER (see Figure 8). MAIER manufactures components for the major car makers in the automotive industry (e.g Opel, Toyota, Honda, PSA, etc.). Those are well established companies in the market representing a more conservative approach when it comes to business model innovation and transition towards circular economy, which is also directly affecting the demonstrator of MAIER in Ecobulk project. In this study, two different types of products will be compared:

- ECOBULK products developed following a circular approach, including two new fascia prototypes whose back sides incorporate 50% recycled ABS (rABS) and 50% recycled PP (rPP), respectively.
- BASELINE products currently developed under a linear model, i.e. the conventional fascia counterparts that are entirely made of virgin plastics.

The social impacts for both ECOBULK and BASELINE products were calculated using the social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) methodology, identifying their main social hotspots (i.e., locations or activities in the supply chain with high social risk/impact). A cradle-to-site assessment was applied, meaning that the scope of the social impact assessment cover from the extraction and processing of raw materials (including closed-loop recycled plastics) to the delivery of the finished automotive parts at the production site where they will be used for assembly in the car. Inventory data associated with these life cycle stages and processes were gathered from Deliverable 7.2 (Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Costs), which were then processed and used as input data to perform the S-LCA. In particular, the characterisation method, social indicators and datasets of the Social Hotspots Database (SHDB) were used for the S-LCA. It allowed to calculate social impacts for 25 social subcategories grouped into 5 categories, which in turn were aggregated into a single global social footprint for the products (the so-called Social Hotspot Index or SHI).

This report shows the comparative S-LCA of the automotive products targeted (ECOBULK vs BASELINE), showing the main methodological aspects and assumptions made, the results obtained and their analysis, interpretation and conclusions.

Figure 8: MAIER's central console panel

Additionally, a survey is conducted to consider different ways to evaluate the perception of consumers regarding recycled materials and/or products containing recycled materials. This questionnaire is framed within another of the project demonstrators, the Microcab modular vehicle (see Figure 9). The main design strategy for Microcab is modularity and fasteners in order to increase product functionality and foster upgrade, reuse, refurbishment, recycling and recovery through clear dismantling strategies. This design strategy is driven mostly by the leasing business model that Microcab will be implementing for the new H2EV vehicles. The results and conclusions of the survey are discussed in detail in Appendix 10.

Figure 9: Microcab's dashboard fascia switch panel

2.6.1.2 Goal and scope definition

This study aims to calculate the social footprint of the new automotive products developed at ECOBULK. These were produced under a circular economy approach that enabled to incorporate a partial content of closed-loop recycled plastics in the new products. The scope of the study also includes the investigation of the current linear counterparts, which are entirely made of virgin plastics. The social impacts of the new and current products can thus be compared with each other.

The goal of the study is therefore twofold:

- To determine if the new automotive products developed in ECOBULK can generate social benefits compared to the current products.
- To identify the main social hotspots of both current and new products in order to propose opportunities for social improvement.

Of course, this is fully aligned with the main circular economy objectives that ECOBULK automotive sector demonstrator has (see D8.3):

- The development of new sustainable materials for composites to use in mass production in the automotive sector (e.g. bio-based reinforced fibres and bio-resin, jute fibres and PP resin, non-woven textiles using bio-based or secondary raw materials);
- The development of composite moulding techniques to support the use of more sustainable raw materials in aesthetic interior and structural automotive components;
- The design of internal car parts to prolonged component life and enable component reuse; and,
- Sorting and separating of plastic elements from ELV shredded waste streams.

The S-LCA will be aligned as much as possible on goal and scope definition of LCC and LCA, depending the availability of social data.

2.6.1.2.1 System boundaries definition

The scope of the S-LCA study includes the supply chain of the target products, assessing their potential social impacts 'from the cradle to the site'. This cradle-to-site scope encompasses from the extraction and processing of raw materials (including closed-loop recycled plastics) to the delivery of the finished automotive parts at the production site where they will be assembled in the car. Figure 10 shows the system boundaries established in the present study, including the life cycle stages and processes included and excluded.

Hence, cradle-to-site scope refers to the social footprint produced over cradle-to-gate plus the transportation from the product factory gate to assembly site (car factory). The use and end-of-life stages are, however, excluded from the S-LCA study under this cradle-to-site approach.

Figure 10. System boundaries: cradle-to-site = cradle-to-gate + distribution.

2.6.1.2.2 Functional Unit

The functional unit defines quantitatively the object of a study. It is particularly relevant in comparative studies, since it ensures that the product alternatives considered are compared on an equivalent basis. Defining the functional unit is also important for determining the reference flow, which translates the functional unit into specific product flows for each product alternative and enables to identify the material inputs necessary for the fulfilment of the functional unit in each case (UNEP, 2020).

In order to define the functional unit, it is helpful to first clearly identify the product to be investigated, including its main functions and product utility. The product investigated herein is a central console fascia for Dacia Lodge, whose function is to serve as a decorative panel to house the central console elements assembled in the car dashboard, ensuring proper safety and aesthetics. Therefore, the **functional unit can be defined in this study as a given number of units of central console fascia** (one product unit would be preferable as in the environmental LCA study, see Deliverable 7.2). This functional unit make it possible to compare the different types of products investigated (Table 2):

- ECOBULK products developed following a circular approach, including two new fascia prototypes whose back sides incorporate 50% recycled ABS (rABS) and 50% recycled PP (rPP), respectively.
- BASELINE products currently developed under a linear model, i.e. the conventional fascia counterparts that are entirely made of virgin plastics.

It is normally necessary to define the functional unit in monetary terms to use a S-LCA database because of the trade models applied, such as the GTAP model used in the SHDB. There were no data available for the production

costs per unit of each fascia model due to confidentiality issues. Consequently, the functional unit could not be set to one product unit. However, industry partner (MAIER) provided a percentage breakdown of the total production costs for each fascia model, as well as the percentage relationships between the production costs of the different models. This production cost relationships were used to compare the social footprint of the different fascia models investigated, as shown in Table 2; e.g., 1 USD of ABS baseline product (#10) can thus be fairly compared with 1.11 USD of PLA baseline product (#11).

Table 2. Description of the product systems (central console fascia models) under study.

Product type/scenario	Product name (code)	Product on cost ⁽¹⁾ %	Total weight kg	Composition	
				Front side	Back side
BASELINE	ABS baseline (#10): ABS / ABS-GF8	100	0.238	100% virgin ABS	92% virgin ABS with 8% glass fibre
	PLA baseline (#11): ABS / PLA-T10	111.04	0.276	100% virgin ABS	90% virgin PLA with 10% talcum
	PP baseline (#14): P/E-T22 / PP-NF30	129.07	0.244	78% virgin P/E with 22% talcum	70% virgin PP with 30% natural fibre
ECOBULK	ECOABS-R2 (#34): ABS / ABS-R2	101.41	0.237	100% virgin ABS	50% virgin ABS with 50% recycled ABS
	ECOPLA-R2 (#36): ABS / PLA-R2 ⁽²⁾	115.12	0.294	100% virgin ABS	50% virgin PLA with 50% recycled PLA
	ECOPP-R2 (#38): P/E-T22 / PP-R2	119.82	0.240	78% virgin P/E with 22% talcum	50% virgin PP with 50% recycled PP

(1) Total production costs for each product are expressed as a percentage of the total production costs of the ABS baseline product (#10).

(2) The ECOPLA-R2 product (#36) was finally excluded from the S-LCA study because it showed a lack of structural functionality during mechanical testing.

2.6.1.3 Social life cycle inventory: S-LCI

Primary data provided by industry partner (MAIER) were used as the starting point to conduct the S-LCA. Specifically, it provided a percentage breakdown of the production costs for each fascia model, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Production costs for the products under study (% in relation to the total production costs of the ABS baseline product).

Cost component	ABS baseline (#10)	PLA baseline (#11)	PP baseline (#14)	ECOABS- R2 (#34)	ECOPP-R2 (#38)
MATERIALS	20.52	23.11	43.67	21.64	36.29
Plastics	10.39	12.98	10.12	11.51	12.27
Paints & coatings	7.11	7.11	30.53	7.11	21.00
Fixations	2.79	2.79	2.79	2.79	2.79
Packaging	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23
MANUFACTURING	63.01	69.17	63.01	63.01	63.01
Injection moulding	18.50	24.66	18.50	18.50	18.50
Painting	20.92	20.92	20.92	20.92	20.92
Assembly & packaging	23.59	23.59	23.59	23.59	23.59
DEFECTIVES	16.47	18.76	22.39	16.75	20.52
Defectives, materials	16.33	18.57	22.25	16.60	20.37
Defectives, operations	0.14	0.19	0.14	0.15	0.15
TOTAL	100.00	111.04	129.07	101.40	119.82

The production cost breakdown was further disaggregated in more detail by considering the inputs/outputs collected in the life cycle inventory developed for the environmental LCA study (see Deliverable 7.2). The inventory data were combined with market prices for raw materials, energy and waste management (available in Annex II), resulting in a more detailed production cost breakdown for each fascia model (see column 'Recalculated cost' in Table 4-Table 8).

Finally, the information on production costs was complemented with other supply chain data to completely define the S-LCI of each fascia model, as shown in Table 4-Table 8. To this end, industry partner (MAIER) identified the Tier 1 supplier and/or production location for each raw material and component of the fascia models (see column 'Production country (company)' in Table 4-Table 8).

Table 4. S-LCI of the ABS baseline product (#10).

Component	Description	Amount (per product unit)	Aggregated cost (%)	Recalculated cost (%)	Sector	Production country (company)
Front side	Virgin ABS	0.1028 kg	10.39	4.74	Plastic products	Spain (ELIX Polymers)
Back side	Virgin ABS-GF8	0.1253 kg		5.65	Plastic products	Germany (INEOS Styrolution)
Paint P8227	Polyurethane	0.003 kg	7.11	5.33	Plastic products	France
Hardener P1040	Chemicals	0.001 kg		1.78	Chemical products	France
Fixations	Metal	0.006 kg	2.79	2.79	Metal products	Spain
Packaging (reusable collapsible pallet-box)	Box (cardboard)	4 g	0.23	0.20	Paper products	Spain
	Pallet (wood)	0.3 g		0.02	Wood products	Spain
	Can (steel)	0.1 g		0.01	Metal products	Spain
Manufacturing	Electricity	17.078 kWh	63.01	28.16	Electricity	Spain
	Natural gas	0.39 m ³		1.89	Gas manufacture/ distrib.	Spain
	Operations	-		32.88	Motor vehicles and parts	Spain (MAIER)
Product distribution	Road, truck	0.077 tkm		0.08	Transport	Spain
Externally managed waste	Plastic scrap	22 g	16.47	16.45	Recycling (internal)	Spain
	Waste paint sludge	0.2 g		0.00	Waste treatment	Spain
	Packaging waste	4.4 g		0.02	Waste treatment	Spain
TOTAL	Cradle-to- site	-	100.00	100.00	-	-

Table 5. S-LCI of the PLA baseline product (#11).

Component	Description	Amount (per product unit)	Aggregated cost (%)	Recalculated cost (%)	Sector	Production country (company)
Front side	Virgin ABS	0.1028 kg	12.98	4.74 (4.27)	Plastic products	Spain (ELIX Polymers)
Back side	Virgin PLA-T10	0.1628 kg		8.24 (7.42)	Plastic products	Thailand/USA (TECNARO) ⁽¹⁾
Paint P8227	Polyurethane	0.003 kg	7.11	5.33 (4.80)	Plastic products	France
Hardener P1040	Chemicals	0.001 kg		1.78 (1.60)	Chemical products	France
Fixations	Metal	0.006 kg	2.79	2.79 (2.51)	Metal products	Spain
Packaging (reusable collapsible pallet-box)	Box (cardboard)	5 g	0.23	0.21 (0.19)	Paper products	Spain
	Pallet (wood)	0.3 g		0.01 (0.01)	Wood products	Spain
	Can (steel)	0.1 g		0.00 (0.00)	Metal products	Spain
Manufacturing	Electricity	17.078 kWh	69.17	28.16 (25.37)	Electricity	Spain
	Natural gas	0.39 m ³		1.89 (1.70)	Gas manufacture/ distrib.	Spain
	Operations	-		39.02 (35.14)	Motor vehicles and parts	Spain (MAIER)
Product distribution	Road, truck	0.090 tkm		0.10 (0.09)	Transport	Spain
Externally managed waste	Plastic scrap	22 g	18.76	18.74 (16.88)	Recycling (internal)	Spain
	Waste paint sludge	0.2 g		0.00 (0.00)	Waste treatment	Spain
	Packaging waste	5.4 g		0.02 (0.02)	Waste treatment	Spain
TOTAL	Cradle-to- site	-	111.04	111.04 (100.00)	-	-

(1) TECNARO has facilities in Germany where it produces plastic compounds by mixing polymers, additives, fillers and/or reinforcing fibres purchased from other suppliers. Two different countries were assumed herein for the production of PLA (which is the main raw material in PLA-T10 compound) according to the location of the production plants of two major PLA producers: Thailand (Total Corbion PLA) and USA (NatureWorks).

Table 6. S-LCI of the PP baseline product (#14).

Component	Description	Amount (per product unit)	Aggregated cost (%)	Recalculated cost (%)	Sector	Production country (company)
Front side	Virgin P/E-T22	0.1028 kg	10.12	4.52 (3.50)	Plastic products	Spain (LyondellBasell)
Back side	Virgin PP-NF30	0.1280 kg		5.60 (4.34)	Plastic products	Germany (TECNARO) ⁽¹⁾
Primer P00282	Chemicals	0.001 kg	30.53	4.36 (3.38)	Chemical products	Germany
Paint P7433	Chemicals	0.003 kg		13.09 (10.14)	Chemical products	Germany
Thinner P00054	Chemicals	0.001 kg		4.36 (3.38)	Chemical products	Germany
Hardener P7421	Chemicals	0.001 kg		4.36 (3.38)	Chemical products	Germany
Thinner P00053	Chemicals	0.001 kg		4.36 (3.38)	Chemical products	Germany
Fixations	Metal	0.006 kg		2.79	2.79 (2.16)	Metal products
Packaging (reusable collapsible pallet-box)	Box (cardboard)	2.9 g	0.23	0.09 (0.07)	Paper products	Spain
	Pallet (wood)	4 g		0.13 (0.10)	Wood products	Spain
	Can (steel)	0.2 g		0.01 (0.01)	Metal products	Spain
Manufacturing	Electricity	17.078 kWh	63.01	28.16 (21.82)	Electricity	Spain
	Natural gas	0.39 m ³		1.89 (1.46)	Gas manufacture/distrib.	Spain
	Operations	-		32.88 (25.47)	Motor vehicles and parts	Spain (MAIER)
Product distribution	Road, truck	0.073 tkm		0.08 (0.06)	Transport	Spain
Externally managed waste	Plastic scrap	22 g	22.39	22.34 (17.31)	Recycling (internal)	Spain
	Waste paint sludge	0.2 g		0.00 (0.00)	Waste treatment	Spain
	Packaging waste	7.1 g		0.05 (0.04)	Waste treatment	Spain
TOTAL	Cradle-to-site	-	129.08	129.08 (100.00)	-	-

(1) TECNARO has facilities in Germany where it produces plastic compounds by mixing polymers, additives, fillers and/or reinforcing fibres purchased from other suppliers. The production of virgin PP-NF30 was assumed to take place in Germany since there are major PP producers with production plants there (e.g., LyondellBasell).

Table 7. S-LCI of the ECOABS-R2 product (#34).

Component	Description	Amount (per product unit)	Aggregated cost (%)	Recalculated cost (%)	Sector	Production country (company)
Front side	Virgin ABS	0.1028 kg	11.51	4.74 (4.67)	Plastic products	Spain (ELIX Polymers)
Back side	ABS-R2 (50% rABS)	0.1242 kg		6.77 (6.68)	ELV plastics recycling	Spain (BELLVER PLA)
Paint P8227	Polyurethane	0.003 kg	7.11	5.33 (5.26)	Plastic products	France
Hardener P1040	Chemicals	0.001 kg		1.78 (1.75)	Chemical products	France
Fixations	Metal	0.006 kg	2.79	2.79 (2.75)	Metal products	Spain
Packaging (reusable collapsible pallet-box)	Box (cardboard)	4 g	0.23	0.20 (0.21)	Paper products	Spain
	Pallet (wood)	0.3 g		0.02 (0.02)	Wood products	Spain
	Can (steel)	0.1 g		0.01 (0.01)	Metal products	Spain
Manufacturing	Electricity	17.078 kWh	63.01	28.16 (27.77)	Electricity	Spain
	Natural gas	0.39 m ³		1.89 (1.87)	Gas manufacture/ distrib.	Spain
	Operations	-		32.88 (32.41)	Motor vehicles and parts	Spain (MAIER)
Product distribution	Road, truck	0.077 tkm		0.08 (0.08)	Transport	Spain
Externally managed waste	Plastic scrap	22 g	16.75	16.73 (16.51)	Recycling (internal)	Spain
	Waste paint sludge	0.2 g		0.00 (0.00)	Waste treatment	Spain
	Packaging waste	4.4 g		0.02 (0.01)	Waste treatment	Spain
TOTAL	Cradle-to- site	-	101.41	101.41 (100.00)	-	-

Table 8. S-LCI of the ECOPP-R2 product (#38).

Component	Description	Amount (per product unit)	Aggregated cost (%)	Recalculated cost (%)	Sector	Production country (company)
Front side	Virgin P/E-T22	0.1028 kg	12.27	4.52 (3.77)	Plastic products	Spain (LyondellBasell)
Back side	PP-R2 (50% rPP)	0.1242 kg		7.75 (6.47)	ELV plastics recycling	Spain (BELLVER PLA)
Primer P00282	Chemicals	0.001 kg	21.00	3.00 (2.50)	Chemical products	Germany
Paint P7433	Chemicals	0.003 kg		9.00 (7.51)	Chemical products	Germany
Thinner P00054	Chemicals	0.001 kg		3.00 (2.50)	Chemical products	Germany
Hardener P7421	Chemicals	0.001 kg		3.00 (2.50)	Chemical products	Germany
Thinner P00053	Chemicals	0.001 kg		3.00 (2.50)	Chemical products	Germany
Fixations	Metal	0.006 kg	2.79	2.79 (2.33)	Metal products	Spain
Packaging (reusable collapsible pallet-box)	Box (cardboard)	2.9 g	0.23	0.09 (0.08)	Paper products	Spain
	Pallet (wood)	4 g		0.13 (0.11)	Wood products	Spain
	Can (steel)	0.2 g		0.01 (0.01)	Metal products	Spain
Manufacturing	Electricity	17.078 kWh	63.01	28.16 (23.51)	Electricity	Spain
	Natural gas	0.39 m ³		1.89 (1.58)	Gas manufacture/distrib.	Spain
	Operations	-		32.88 (27.44)	Motor vehicles and parts	Spain (MAIER)
Product distribution	Road, truck	0.078 tkm		0.08 (0.07)	Transport	Spain
Externally managed waste	Plastic scrap	22 g	20.52	20.47 (17.08)	Recycling (internal)	Spain
	Waste paint sludge	0.2 g		0.00 (0.00)	Waste treatment	Spain
	Packaging waste	7.1 g		0.05 (0.04)	Waste treatment	Spain
TOTAL	Cradle-to-site	-	119.82	119.82 (100.00)	-	-

As explained in Section 2.2, the SHDB can be used to automatize the S-LCIA phase, using generic data for social indicators linked to 57 sectors in 140 regions/countries. Most of the sectors identified in the S-LCI (see column 'sector' in Table 4-Table 8) were available and totally characterised in the SHDB, including chemicals and plastic materials, metal products, electricity, gas manufacture and distribution, motor vehicles and parts, transport, paper and wood products. Waste management sector was, however, missing in the SHDB, so there were no generic data for social indicators linked to recycling and other waste treatment operations.

On the one hand, it was decided to exclude the waste treatment operations applied to plastic scrap, waste paint sludge and packaging waste. This exclusion is not expected to significantly affect the results, especially the comparative ones, since the scenarios to be compared present similar amounts for these operations. These were indeed excluded in the environmental LCA as well, assuming that plastic scrap may be reintroduced in the manufacturing process, while the other wastes are negligible.

On the other hand, the recycling of plastics from end-of-life vehicles (ELV) could not be excluded from the S-LCA study. ELV plastics recycling was expected to have a relevant effect on the results, since it was the main differentiating element between the scenarios to be compared as well as a core element of the ECOBULK project. Hence, a S-LCI had to be modelled specifically for the ELV plastics recycling sector.

ELV plastics recycling

The S-LCI for plastics recycling from ELV was developed using cost data for the recycling process applied in ECOBULK, which were directly gathered from the LCC study (available in Deliverable 7.2). These cost data were based on primary data provided by partners involved in the plastics recycling process (BELLVER PLA and AIMPLAS), secondary data and assumptions. Table 9 shows the S-LCI developed for the ELV plastics recycling process, distinguishing between ABS and PP recycling. The product obtained from the recycling process is a plastic compound with 50% recycled content, either ABS-R2 or PP-R2, which contain 50% rABS and 50% rPP, respectively.

Table 9. S-LCI of ELV plastics recycling to obtain ABS-R2 and PP-R2.

Cost component	Recycling cost (%)		Sector	Production country
	ABS-R2	PP-R2		
Virgin polymer	60.65	54.55	Plastic products	Spain
1 st shredding, electricity	15.72	17.44	Electricity	Spain
2 nd shredding + 1 st extrusion, electricity	4.00	4.73	Electricity	Spain
Compounding, electricity	3.01	3.57	Electricity	Spain
1 st shredding, labour	4.70	5.58	Plastic products (used as approach)	Spain
2 nd shredding + 1 st extrusion, labour	4.47	5.30	Plastic products (used as approach)	Spain
Compounding, labour	7.45	8.83	Plastic products (used as approach)	Spain

2.6.1.4 Social impact assessment: S-LCIA results and interpretation

Below are shown and discussed the main results of the S-LCIA. The results of the social footprint of each fascia model investigated are shown first, as well as the breakdown by social impact categories and subcategories, identifying the social hotspots in each case. Subsequently, the social impacts obtained for the new fascia models developed in ECOBULK are compared with the impacts of their virgin equivalent counterparts to determine the social benefits that can be derived from the project.

2.6.1.4.1 S-LCIA of the ABS baseline product (#10)

Table 10 shows the SHI obtained for the ABS baseline product (#10), as well as its breakdown into the different social impact categories that contribute to the total social footprint. Note that 1 USD of product was used as the reference flow in this case.

Table 10. Social impacts for 1 USD of the ABS baseline product (#10) by impact category.

Social category	Total impact (Mrheq)
Labour rights & decent work	3.95
Health & safety	5.04
Human rights	2.67

Social category	Total impact (Mrheq)
Governance	4.12
Community	2.81
TOTAL: SHI	18.59

The total social footprint of the ABS baseline product is estimated at 18.59 Mrheq/USD. Figure 11 and Figure 12 graphically show the contribution that each social impact category and subcategory has on the total social footprint. In addition, it can be observed how each Tier 1-level CSS contributes to the different social impact categories and subcategories, as well as the CSS contribution to the total social footprint (Figure 13).

The sectors with the largest social impacts are vehicle parts and electricity in Spain. This was expected since they are by far the CSS with the highest share in the production costs of the ABS baseline product. The contribution of Spanish electricity to the social impact categories ranges from 22.7% to 29.9% (depending on the impact category), being comparable to its production cost share (28.2%, Table 4), so the social risk levels are acceptable. The vehicle parts sector, involving the operations in the fascia production site in Spain, shows a contribution to the social impact categories of 42.4-52.0%, being significantly higher than its production cost share (32.9%, Table 4). Vehicle parts sector in Spain was thus identified as a social hotspot of the ABS baseline product, so the social risks in the specific site should be evaluated in more detail to check if they are actually high and then look for social improvement opportunities there. Special attention should be paid to excessive working time and unemployment, among other aspects (Figure 12). Similarly, the plastic products sector in Spain (linked to virgin ABS production in this case) has social impact contributions (6.3-6.9%) above its production cost share (4.7%, Table 4), so the social risks in this sector should be addressed in more detail too.

Figure 11. Social impacts for 1 USD of the ABS baseline product (#10) by impact category.

Figure 12. CSS contribution to social impacts of the ABS baseline product (#10) by impact subcategory.

Figure 13. Social impacts for 1 USD of the ABS baseline product (#10) by CSS, including Tier 1 level.

Finally, the social impacts were analysed in more detail by considering the whole supply chain, including not only Tier 1-level CSS but also the other CSS related to lower-Tier suppliers. The GTAP model (included in the SHDB) was used to this end, since it provides the trade flows between the economic sectors of each country/region, thus allowing to model the economic relationships between Tier 1-level CSS and other tier n-level CSS involved in the supply chain. The results of this supply chain assessment are summarised in Figure 14. It can be found that vehicle parts and electricity in Spain still remain as the most relevant CSS (with 8.1% and 4.2% of total SHI, respectively), although there are other CSS emerging now as relevant in social terms like business services in Spain and India (3.0% and 2.2%), among other.

Figure 14. Supply chain contribution to total social footprint (SHI) of the ABS baseline product (#10), including Tier n level (cut-off = 1%, remaining CSS aggregated in the bottom bar).

2.6.1.4.2 S-LCIA of the PLA baseline product (#11)

Table 11 shows the SHI obtained for the PLA baseline product (#11), as well as its breakdown into the different social impact categories that contribute to the total social footprint. In this case, two alternative scenarios were assessed, which only differ in the country where the PLA material is produced (USA vs Thailand). Note that 1 USD of product was used as the reference flow in both cases.

Table 11. Social impacts for 1 USD of the PLA baseline product (#11) by impact category.

Social category	Total impact (Mrheq)	
	PLA baseline product (#11) USA	PLA baseline product (#11) Thailand
Labour rights & decent work	4.34	6.25
Health & safety	5.36	6.45
Human rights	2.87	4.44
Governance	4.22	6.97
Community	3.03	4.25
TOTAL: SHI	19.82	28.36

The total social footprint of the PLA baseline product depends largely on the PLA production scenarios, varying from 19.82 to 28.36 Mrheq/USD for the USA and Thailand scenarios, respectively. The social footprint of the PLA baseline product can thus increase up to 43.1% if the PLA material used in the fascia is produced in Thailand instead of USA.

Figure 15-Figure 17 graphically show the contribution that each social impact category, subcategory and Tier 1-level CSS has on the total social footprint. The sectors with the largest contribution are vehicle parts, electricity and PLA production, either in USA or Thailand. These sectors have the highest share in the production costs of the PLA baseline product. The social impacts of the electricity consumed for fascia production are not a matter of concern: the contribution of Spanish electricity to the social impact categories (19.2-25.1% for USA scenario and 14.3-17.8% for Thailand scenario) is quite below its production cost share (25.4%, Table 5), meaning that the social risk levels in this CSS are admissible. Conversely, the vehicle parts sector shows a contribution to the social impact categories (42.1-52.2% for USA scenario and 28.0-43.5% for Thailand scenario) higher than its production cost share (35.1%, Table 5). Vehicle parts sector in Spain is hence identified as a social hotspot of the PLA baseline product, so the social risks in the specific site should be evaluated in more detail to check if they are actually high and then look for opportunities and measures for social improvements there. Considering the results for the social impact subcategories (Figure 16),

special attention should be paid to aspects like unemployment, occupational toxics and hazards, injuries and fatalities.

The social impacts of PLA used in the fascia depend on where this material is produced, being the reason for such huge differences between the social impacts of both scenarios assessed for the PLA baseline product. The use of PLA can be a concern because the social impacts of the PLA are higher than the cost share (7.4% of total production costs, Table 5). This is specially alarming for PLA produced in Thailand, which represents 26.5-45.2% of total social footprint, whilst the PLA produced in USA limits to 9.6-14.9%. PLA production sector, especially in Thailand, is therefore a social hotspot of the PLA baseline product. There could then be great opportunities to implement social improvements by working together with PLA suppliers in USA or Thailand. The social risks in the specific sites of the PLA suppliers should be evaluated in more detail to look for opportunities and measures for social improvements there.

Figure 15. Social impacts for 1 USD of the PLA baseline product (#11) by impact category, including both scenarios for PLA production: USA (top) and Thailand (bottom).

Figure 16. CSS contribution to social impacts of the PLA baseline product (#11) by impact subcategory, including both scenarios for PLA production: USA (top) and Thailand (bottom).

PLA baseline (#11) USA

Figure 17. Social impacts for 1 USD of the PLA baseline product (#11) by CSS (Tier 1 level), including both scenarios for PLA production: USA (top) and Thailand (bottom).

Figure 18 shows the supply chain contribution to the total social footprint of the PLA baseline product, including not only Tier 1-level CSS but also the other CSS related to lower-Tier suppliers. Vehicle parts and electricity in Spain and plastic products in USA still remain as the most relevant CSS for the USA scenario (with 8.1%, 3.5% and 4.3% of total SHI, respectively), but other CSS appear now as relevant, such as business services in Spain and India (2.7% and 2.0%), among other. The CSS with the largest contribution to the total SHI for the Thailand scenario is by far the Thailand plastic products sector (22.6%), followed by vehicle parts and electricity in Spain (5.7% and 2.5%), trade in Thailand (2.3%) and business services in Spain (1.9%).

PLA baseline (#11) USA

PLA baseline (#11) Thailand

Figure 18. Supply chain (Tier n level) contribution to total social footprint (SHI) of the PLA baseline product (#11) (cut-off = 1%, remaining CSS aggregated in the bottom bar), including both scenarios for PLA production: USA (top) and Thailand (bottom).

2.6.1.4.3 S-LCIA of the PP baseline product (#14)

Table 12 shows the SHI obtained for the PP baseline product (#14), as well as its breakdown into the different social impact categories that contribute to the total social footprint. Note that 1 USD of product was used as the reference flow in this case.

Table 12. Social impacts for 1 USD of the PP baseline product (#14) by impact category.

Social category	Total impact (Mrheq)
Labour rights & decent work	3.69
Health & safety	4.75
Human rights	2.55
Governance	3.90
Community	2.61
TOTAL: SHI	17.50

The total social footprint of the PP baseline product is estimated at 17.50 Mrheq/USD. Figure 19-Figure 21 graphically show the contribution that each social impact category, subcategory and Tier 1-level CSS has on the total social footprint.

Most of the social impacts are caused by the following CSS: chemical products in Germany, vehicle parts in Spain and electricity in Spain. These CSS together comprise 84.0% of the total social footprint, while their joint contribution to the social impact categories ranges from 83.1% to 85.0% (depending on the impact category). The chemical products manufactured in Germany contribute to the social impact categories with 22.7-24.8%, which is comparable to their production cost share (23.7%, Table 6). The same happens with the Spanish electricity consumed for fascia production, showing a contribution to the social impact categories (18.7-25.0%) that is fully aligned with its production cost share (21.8%, Table 6). Hence, the great contribution of the German chemical products and Spanish electricity to the total social footprint is basically due to the fact that these CSS are very present in the production of the PP baseline product. However, in view of the ratios between impact and cost shares, these CSS do not seem to have social risk levels of high concern. The vehicle parts sector, which involves the operations in the fascia production site in Spain, contributes to the social impact categories with 35.4-42.8%, being high compared to its production cost share (25.5%, Table 6). Vehicle parts sector in Spain can thus be identified as a social hotspot of the PP baseline product. The social risks in the specific fascia production site should be evaluated in more detail to check if they are actually high and then look for opportunities and measures for social improvements there. Special attention should be paid to aspects like

unemployment and excessive working, among others (Figure 20). Likewise, the plastic products sector in Spain (related to virgin PP production in this case) shows social impact contributions (4.9-5.5%) that are high compared to its production cost share (4.3%, Table 6), so the social risks related to this sector should be addressed in more detail too. This CSS has, however, lower priority since its contribution to the total social impact is quite limited.

Figure 19. Social impacts for 1 USD of the PP baseline product (#14) by impact category.

Figure 20. CSS contribution to social impacts of the PP baseline product (#14) by impact subcategory.

Figure 21. Social impacts for 1 USD of the PP baseline product (#14) by CSS, including Tier 1 level.

Figure 22 shows the supply chain contribution to the total social footprint of the PP baseline product, including not only Tier 1-level CSS but also the other CSS related to lower-Tier suppliers. As previously explained, vehicle parts and electricity in Spain and chemical products in Germany are the most relevant CSS (with 6.7%, 3.4% and 2.9% of total SHI, respectively). There are, however, other CSS emerging now as relevant in social terms, such as business services in Spain and India (2.4% and 2.3%), among other.

Figure 22. Supply chain contribution to total social footprint (SHI) of the PP baseline product (#14), including Tier n level (cut-off = 1%, remaining CSS aggregated in the bottom bar).

2.6.1.4.4 S-LCIA of the ECOABS-R2 product (#34)

Table 13 shows the SHI obtained for the ECOABS-R2 product (#34), as well as its breakdown into the different social impact categories that contribute to the total social footprint. Note that 1 USD of product was used as the reference flow in this case.

Table 13. Social impacts for 1 USD of the ECOABS-R2 product (#34) by impact category.

Social category	Total impact (Mrheq)
Labour rights & decent work	4.04
Health & safety	5.11
Human rights	2.72
Governance	4.20
Community	2.89
TOTAL: SHI	18.96

The total social footprint of the ECOABS-R2 product is estimated at 18.96 Mrheq/USD. Figure 23-Figure 25 graphically show the contribution that each social impact category, subcategory and Tier 1-level CSS has on the total social footprint.

The S-LCIA results for the ECOABS-R2 product are very similar to those obtained for the ABS baseline product. The CSS causing most of the social impacts are vehicle parts and electricity in Spain, which are again the ones with the highest share in the production costs. The electricity consumed for fascia production has a 22.1%-28.7% contribution to the social impact categories, which is aligned with its production cost share (27.8%, Table 7). The social risk levels for this CSS can thus be considered as acceptable. The vehicle parts sector, which comprises the operations in the fascia production site in Spain, contributes to the social impact categories with 35.4-42.8%. The social impact contributions of the Spanish vehicle parts sector are high in relation to its share in the production costs of the ECOABS-R2 product (32.4%, Table 7), meaning that this CSS can be considered as a social hotspot again. Social risks in the specific site should be carefully evaluated, paying special attention to aspects like unemployment and excessive working time, in view of the results for the social impact subcategories (Figure 24).

Furthermore, the plastic products and ELV plastics recycling sectors in Spain can be deemed as social hotspots as well, although they have less priority due to their limited social impacts. The plastic products sector in Spain (related to virgin ABS in this case) has a 6.1-6.6% contribution to the social impact categories, whilst the ELV plastics recycling sector (linked to recycled ABS-R2) contributes with 7.9-8.9%. The social impact contributions of these

CSS are above their shares in the total production costs (4.7% and 6.7% for virgin and recycled ABS, respectively; Table 7).

Figure 23. Social impacts for 1 USD of the ECOABS-R2 product (#34) by impact category.

Figure 24. CSS contribution to social impacts of the ECOABS-R2 product (#34) by impact subcategory.

Figure 25. Social impacts for 1 USD of the ECOABS-R2 product (#34) by CSS, including Tier 1 level.

Figure 26 shows the supply chain contribution to the total social footprint of the ECOABS-R2 product, including not only Tier 1-level CSS but also the other CSS related to lower-Tier suppliers. The CSS with the largest contribution to the total SHI are the vehicle parts and electricity in Spain (7.8% and 4.3%), followed by business services and plastic products in Spain (3.2% and 2.4%) and business services in India (2.2%).

Figure 26. Supply chain contribution to total social footprint (SHI) of the ECOABS-R2 product (#34), including Tier n level (cut-off = 1%, remaining CSS aggregated in the bottom bar).

2.6.1.4.5 S-LCIA of the ECOPP-R2 product (#38)

Table 14 shows the SHI obtained for the ECOPP-R2 product (#38), as well as its breakdown into the different social impact categories that contribute to the total social footprint. Note that 1 USD of product was used as the reference flow in this case.

Table 14. Social impacts for 1 USD of the ECOPP-R2 product (#38) by impact category.

Social category	Total impact (Mrheq)
Labour rights & decent work	3.86
Health & safety	4.91
Human rights	2.64
Governance	4.03
Community	2.74
TOTAL: SHI	18.18

The total social footprint of the ECOPP-R2 product is estimated at 18.18 Mrheq/USD. Figure 27-Figure 29 graphically show the contribution that each social impact category, subcategory and Tier 1-level CSS has on the total social footprint.

The S-LCIA results for the ECOPP-R2 product are similar to those obtained for the PP baseline product. The CSS causing most of the social impacts in this case are chemical products in Germany, vehicle parts in Spain and electricity in Spain, which together comprise around 80% of the total social footprint. The contribution of the German chemical products to the social impact categories is now limited to 16.0-17.7%, which is fully aligned with their production cost share (17.5%, Table 8). The social impact contributions of the Spanish electricity consumed (19.5-25.6%) are also in line with its production cost share (23.5%, Table 8). Neither the chemical products nor the electricity are considered in this case social hotspots, since both CSS show admissible ratios between their social impact and cost shares. On the other hand, the Spanish vehicle parts sector is considered a social hotspot, since its social impact contributions (36.3-44.6%) are higher than its share in the total production costs (27.5%, Table 8). Social risks in the specific fascia production site should be evaluated in more detail, carefully examining aspects like unemployment and excessive working time, among other social subcategories (Figure 29).

Similarly, the plastic products and ELV plastics recycling sectors in Spain can be considered social hotspots, although they have much lower social impacts and less priority. The plastic products sector in Spain (related to virgin PP in this case) has a 5.1-5.7% contribution to the social impact categories, whilst

the ELV plastics recycling sector (linked to recycled PP-R2) contributes with 7.9-9.0%. The social impact contributions of these CSS are above their shares in the total production costs (3.8% and 6.5% for virgin and recycled PP, respectively; Table 8).

Figure 27. Social impacts for 1 USD of the ECOPP-R2 product (#38) by impact category.

Figure 28. CSS contribution to social impacts of the ECOPP-R2 product (#38) by impact subcategory.

Figure 29. Social impacts for 1 USD of the ECOPP-R2 product (#38) by CSS, including Tier 1 level.

Figure 30 shows the supply chain contribution to the total social footprint of the ECOPP-R2 product, including not only Tier 1-level CSS but also the other CSS related to lower-Tier suppliers. The CSS showing the largest contribution to the total SHI are the vehicle parts and electricity in Spain (6.9% and 3.8%), followed by business services in Spain and India (2.9% and 2.3%) and plastic products in Spain (2.2%).

Figure 30. Supply chain contribution to total social footprint (SHI) of the ECOPP-R2 product (#38), including Tier n level (cut-off = 1%, remaining CSS aggregated in the bottom bar).

2.6.1.5 Comparative S-LCA results: ECOBULK vs BASELINE products

Finally, the S-LCA results obtained for the different fascia models were compared with each other. The functional unit used for comparison was defined in monetary terms as the production costs required to produce a certain number of fascia units (unknown, but the same for all fascia models). Table 15 shows the SHI obtained for the five different products being studied according to their respective functional units. It also shows the social footprint breakdown into the different social impact categories. In addition, these comparative results are graphically shown in Figure 31.

Table 15. Social impacts for the products under study according to the functional unit (FU).

Product	FU	Labour rights & decent work	Health & safety	Human rights	Governance	Community	TOTAL: SHI
ABS baseline (#10)	1 USD	3.95	5.04	2.67	4.12	2.81	18.59
ECOABS-R2 (#34)	1.01 USD	4.10	5.18	2.75	4.26	2.93	19.22
PP baseline (#14)	1.29 USD	4.76	6.13	3.29	5.04	3.36	22.58
ECOPP-R2 (#38)	1.20 USD	4.62	5.88	3.16	4.83	3.28	21.77
PLA baseline (#11): USA-Thai	1.11 USD	4.82-6.94	5.96-7.16	3.18-4.93	4.69-7.74	3.36-4.72	22.01-31.49

Figure 31. Comparative S-LCA results for the products under study (according to functional unit).

The comparative S-LCA results showed small differences in terms of social impacts between the ECOBULK products and their conventional counterparts. The differences between both product types are primarily in the use of recycled plastics (rABS or rPP) in the ECOBULK products and in the production costs (see Table 2), which are directly related to the functional unit used for comparison. The production costs for the ABS products are almost the same, while the variation in costs for the PP products is more significant. ECOPP-R2 product shows a 7.2% cost reduction compared to the PP baseline product, which is basically due to lower expenses in paints and coatings. This results in a similar social footprint for both ABS products, being slightly higher in ECOABS-R2 product with 3.4% increase (compared to ABS baseline product). Conversely, the social footprint for the ECOPP-R2 product is reduced by 3.6% (compared to PP baseline product).

The small differences between both product types (ECOBULK and BASELINE) is explained by several reasons:

- The virgin plastics used in the ABS and PP products are produced in Europe (Spain, Germany and France), as well as all the other materials and components-. The social risk levels of these CSS are generally low compared to what could happen with other production regions (see, for instance, the Thai plastic products sector, which increases the social footprint of the PLA product by 43.1% compared to the USA scenario). Hence, the baseline products already have limited social impacts, so it is not so easy that any change in the products can directly lead to significant social improvements.

- The recycled plastic materials were modelled from the LCC study (available in Deliverable 7.2), which was based on operational data on a pilot scale that was not yet optimized. This resulted in production costs higher than those expected for an optimised process running on an industrial scale, and consequently the social impacts estimated for the recycling process (and the derived recycled plastics) are also higher than expected.

A further research step, once the ELV plastics recycling process is totally upscaled and optimised under an industrial scale, may involve to record the operational parameters again and the social indicators of the specific industrial process, instead of using generic data and assumptions. The actual social footprint could then be estimated more accurately, allowing for more reliable comparisons.

2.6.1.6 Conclusions

A S-LCA study was conducted to evaluate the potential social impacts of the new central console fascia prototypes developed in ECOBULK with closed-loop recycled plastics. The new prototypes include two different fascia models, whose back sides incorporated 50% rABS and 50% rPP, respectively. In addition, the social impacts of the new prototypes were compared with the impacts of their conventional fascia counterparts (BASELINE) that are entirely made of virgin plastics (ABS, PLA and PP).

The S-LCA methodology was applied under a cradle-to-site scope, covering from the extraction and processing of raw materials (including closed-loop recycled plastics) to the delivery of the finished automotive parts at the production site where they will be assembled in the car. Inventory data were gathered from previous LCA and LCC studies (available in Deliverable 7.2), which were then processed and used as input data to perform the S-LCA. The method, social indicators and datasets of the SHDB, which was incorporated within SimaPro software, were used to tackle the development of the S-LCA study more effectively. A set of 25 social impact sub-categories were thus assessed, which were grouped into 5 social categories, namely: labour rights & decent work, health & safety, human rights, governance and community. Furthermore, the impacts obtained for these social categories were further aggregated into a single global social footprint (the so-called Social Hotspot Index or SHI).

The S-LCA results obtained for ECOBULK and BASELINE products showed small differences in terms of social footprint between both product types. The social impacts for both ABS products are very similar, being slightly higher in ECOABS-R2 product (3.4% social footprint increase compared to ABS baseline product), whereas the impacts for the ECOPP-R2 product are slightly lower (3.6% social footprint reduction compared to PP baseline product). It should be noted that all the materials and components of the ABS and PP

baseline products have European origin, so that their social risk levels are limited (compared to what could happen with other production regions) and there is less room for big social improvements. In addition, the recycled plastics used in the new fascia prototypes were modelled using pilot-scale data, resulting in social impacts higher than those expected for the optimised industrial process. Therefore, a further modelling step using industrial-scale data (once available) is recommended to obtain more accurate and reliable results for comparisons.

The S-LCA also allowed to identify the main social hotspots for each product targeted in the study. Some country-specific sectors were found as possible social hotspots common to all the fascia products investigated. The Spanish vehicle parts sector, linked to the manufacturing operations in the fascia production site, is the major contributor to social impacts for most product case studies (except for PLA baseline Thailand). It was considered as a potential social hotspot because it shows social impact contributions significantly higher than its production cost shares in all cases. Similarly, the plastic products and ELV plastics recycling sectors in Spain were deemed as potential social hotspots, although they have less priority due to their limited social impacts. At this point, it should be noted that the S-LCA results are in part based on generic social data for country-specific sectors, while social conditions in the specific production sites involved in the actual supply chains of the target products may be different. It is, therefore, recommended to gather primary social data from the specific sites for further evaluation aimed at checking if social risks there are actually high. If so, social improvement opportunities and measures should be then investigated in close collaboration with the suppliers and other relevant stakeholders.

2.6.2 S-LCA : Furniture sector

2.6.2.1 *Furniture prototype*

The Italian company Moretti Compact developed new modular furniture. The main focus of furniture design is modularity, mono-/multi-layer and joints/fasteners in order to increase product functionality and foster upgrade, reuse, refurbishment, recycling and recovery through clear disassembling and dismantling strategies. Following the solutions and products designed in WP2, KEAS will manufacture – and using a more sustainable and low- formaldehyde binder from AkzoNobel - components for Moretti’s product manufacturing in the indoor furniture applications. The concept developed by Moretti Compact consists of cubic elements that could be used to assemble different furniture solutions (desks, chairs, beds, bookshelf cabinets), which is presented in Figure 32. The main idea is to work on the whole life cycle of the product: use of recyclable materials, preference for reusable components, utilization

of elements suitable for disassembling and re assembling (screws, glues), simple lines and shapes, neutral colours.

Figure 32: Prototype of modular furniture from Moretti using cubic elements that can be used and reused for different functions (seating, storage)

2.6.2.2 Goal and scope definition

The ECOBULK furniture sector demonstrator has two main circular economy objectives (see D8.3):

- Development of new low/no formaldehyde particle board with a capability of incorporating more recycled content (wood).
- Production of modular furniture for testing new leasing business models that support product take-back, reuse, repair and material recovery.

The reference flow for the analysis will be one cubic element able to fulfil different functions (seating, bedding, storing) during a period of 7 to 10 years used on a daily basis.

2.6.2.3 System boundaries definition

In order to align S-LCA with the life cycle concept, study covers cradle-to-grave, including the premanufacturing (production of inputs), manufacturing, use and post-use (waste management) steps. Figure 33 provides the value chain configuration and system boundaries for the furniture demonstrator in a business as usual scenario with eco-design efforts.

Figure 33: Business as usual scenario for the furniture demonstrator

S-LCA will first be carried out on this first scenario and according to the data collection it will be renewed on two other business scenarios.

In this task, several subtasks were identified in order to structure the work to be done, even if they are not initially identified as subtasks in the Document of Work. These different topics were presented during the meeting in Italy in M30.

2.6.2.4 Methodology for selecting stakeholders and social issues

Different Social Life Cycle Analysis (S-LCA) methodologies offer many social topics group in several stakeholders. Within the ECOBULK project, the aim is to select the most relevant social topics for each demonstrator of the project. The challenge is that relevant social topics can vary according to the type of product and to the location of manufacturing.

Six categories of stakeholders were considered at the beginning of the process: workers, local communities, users, small-scale entrepreneurs, value chain actors and society

Two surveys were carried out separately:

- a google form questionnaire was sent from on the 5th March 2020 to several organizations specialized in the automotive, construction and furniture sector. After indicating the importance of the different stakeholders, organizations assessed the relevance of all the social topics for each of them. 8 answers were collected, 5 of them for the furniture sector.

Figure 34: Importance of stakeholders for experts in the furniture sector

All stakeholders seem important, in particular workers and users.

For workers, there aren't big differences between each social topics, as shown below. Health and safety is the most relevant social topic according to organizations with the maximum rating. The three less relevant social aspects are remuneration, discrimination and freedom of association and collective bargaining.

Figure 35: Importance of social topics for workers

For the stakeholder Local communities, there aren't big differences between each social topics, but employment is the most relevant social topic with 4.6/5. The less relevant social aspect is the community engagement (3.6/5).

Figure 36: Importance of social topics for local communities

For users, there are significant differences between each social topics. Three social topics are relevant: health, product safety and effectiveness and

comfort with at least 4.4/5. Others social topics (responsible communication, privacy and inclusiveness) are less relevant with at the most 3.4/5.

Figure 37: Importance of social topics for users

For small-scale entrepreneurs, many social topics seem important, there are some differences between each social topics. Health and safety, fair trading relationships and access to services and inputs are most relevant social topics with at least a rating of 4.4/5. Less relevant social topics are women's empowerment (3/5) and land rights (3.4/5).

Figure 38: Importance of social topics for small-scale entrepreneurs

For value chain actors, social topic supplier relationships is the most relevant social topic with a rating of 4.8/5. There aren't big differences between other social topics.

Figure 39: Importance of social topics for value chain actors

For the society stakeholder, the social topic public commitment to sustainability issues is the most relevant social topic with a rating of 4.6/5. Less relevant social topics are the prevention and mitigation of conflicts and technology development (3.8/5).

Figure 40: Importance of social topics for society

- Regarding the importance of users in identifying social issues, they were also asked through a google form questionnaire to evaluate the importance of different social topics. The survey was sent to the partners of the ECOBULK project and gathered 108 responses, 56% of Men and 44% of Women. 42% of the participants are aged between 40 and 54. The people are located in 8 different countries, as shown in Figure 41.

Figure 41: Profile of the end-users respondents to the survey on social topics

The analysis of the results show that:

- Most social topics seem important to end-users.
- Regarding each step of the life cycle of a product, the most important social topics would be:
 - Raw materials: safe working conditions and fair trade conditions in small-scale companies
 - Manufacturing: prohibition of child and forced labour
 - Transport : anti-corruption measures
 - Use: health and safety of users
 - End of life: social responsibility among suppliers

Proportion of social topics considered extremely or very important

Figure 42: Proportion of social topics considered extremely of very important

Figure 43: “Extremely” important social topics associated to each step of the life cycle of a product, for end-users

As a conclusion, four categories of stakeholders are considered instead of six:

- **Workers**
- **Local communities**
- **Users**
- **Value chain actors**

For these stakeholders, social topics were selected as shown in Table 16.

During this period, the social topics were addressed into a several questions for the partners developing the prototype to answer as shown in the following example for the furniture sector. **In total, 52 questions were identified.**

Table 16: Number of questions addressed for each social topic and each stakeholder

| Worker
 |
|---|---|--|---|
| Health and safety: 7 | Health: 5 | Health and safety: 6 | Fair competition: 4 |
| Work-life balance: 6 | Product safety: 5
Responsible communication: 8 | Employment: 6 | Promoting social responsibility: 5 |

2.6.2.5 Assessment

To assess the social impacts of the products, a series of questions were asked, related to the stakeholders and the social topics selected.

Table 17: Questions addressed to each stakeholder and social issue for the furniture sector

Social issue / Stakeholder	Related questions
Health & safety / Workers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The company or facility complies with health and safety standards or local laws. - Workers have access to all the required personal protective equipment. - The occupational health and safety of workers is monitored. - In a case of non-compliance with health and safety standards or local laws, the company or facility has developed a corrective action plan with clear timeline for completion.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The company has a PDCA model in place to proactively protect workers' health and safety, beyond compliance with local laws. - Company's commitments and progress on occupational health and safety are disclosed publicly (to external stakeholders). - The top management of the company has publicly declared/recognised health and safety of workers as key priority and the company aims to the best in class.
<p>Work-life balance / Workers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The company or facility has a policy on flexible working arrangements/working hours/ parental leave. - The company or facility has a system in place to enforce the policy on flexible working arrangements/working hours/ parental leave. - Hours worked in a normal working week, not including overtime, are below the limits set by law or international standards. - Hours worked in a normal working week, including overtime, exceed 48 hours. - Company or facility has a PDCA process in place to promote work-life balance. - The commitments, performance, progress and effectiveness of the PDCA (Plan DO Check Act) programs are reported publicly.
<p>Health / Users</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is solid science-based evidence that normal use of the product enables and significantly contributes to an improved health condition for user in comparison to alternative solutions. - The company has a dossier or other evidence that shows how the product or service has been designed to create a maximum contribution to health of the user and, if applicable, encourage a healthy lifestyle. - The product or service conforms to all national requirements in the markets where the product is offered. - The normal use of the product has negative health impacts on the long run. - Any use of the product has direct negative health on short and long term
<p>Product safety / Users</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is solid science-based evidence that normal use of the product is safer for active or passive users than alternative solutions and that the product or service eliminates a risk in common products and services used for the same purpose. - The company has a dossier or other evidence that shows how the product or service has been

	<p>designed to create maximum safety for active and passive users.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The product conforms to all national requirements regarding product safety. - The normal use of the product or services can cause higher risks compared to alternative solutions. - Any use of the product can be regarded as unsafe.
<p>Responsible communication / Users</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The product is labelled according to the regulations in the country of sale. - The company has a responsible communication policy - A grievance mechanism is in place to enable feedback from users. - No incidents of misleading communication have been found in the last year. - The company adheres to commonly accepted principles. - The communication by the company and its resellers is deliberately designed to avoid misleading claims. - Claims made in marketing and product documentation that the product or its use support a more sustainable lifestyle are all backed up with science-based evidence. 3rd-party market research or research following international and national standards. The evidence is publicly available and easy to access for all users and potential users. - A mechanism in place to engage in dialogues with users and consumers.
<p>Health and safety / Local communities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No incidents of actual damage, adverse impacts or risks to community health and safety have been discovered. - If incidents of actual damage, adverse impacts or risks to community health and safety have been discovered, a corrective action plan with a timeline for completion have been developed by the company or facility. - The company or facility has a policy on local community health and safety to meet the requirements set by local laws or international standards. - The company or facility has a system or mechanism in place to enforce the policy on local community health and safety. - The company or facility has a PDCA programme in place to address health and safety of local communities beyond the requirements set in local laws.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The company or facility publicly reports and discloses its commitments, performance, progress and effectiveness of the PDCA program/initiatives/activities.
<p>Employment / Local communities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The company has publicly committed to grow local employment or at least keep the workforce stable in the long term. - The company actively contributes to skill development in connection to its future need for staffing and the staffing of its subcontractors and smallholders. - The company does not engage in discrimination when hiring new employees. - The company or facility has a policy prioritising buying goods and services from local suppliers. - The company has a policy to create shared value with regional small subcontractors, smallholders or small-scale entrepreneurs, which includes an agreed policy and commitment on: fair working conditions for workers, fair salaries for workers at least on the level of minimum wage, non-discrimination. - These policies are published and a grievance mechanism is in place to handle complaints about how staff is selected and how commitments are handled.
<p>Fair competition / Value chain actors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legal actions pending or completed during the reporting period regarding anticompetitive behavior and violations of anti-trust and monopoly legislation in which the reporting organization has been identified as a participant. The company is part of alliances that behave in an anti-competitive manner. - The company has a documented statement or procedures (policy, strategy etc.) to prevent engaging in or being complicit in anticompetitive behavior. - The company makes its employees aware of the importance of compliance with competition law and fair competition.
<p>Promoting social responsibility / Value chain actors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The company has an explicit code of conduct that protects the rights of workers at suppliers. - The company audits suppliers with regard to social responsibility in the last year. - The company adheres to an initiative that promotes social responsibility throughout the supply chain. - The company supports suppliers in terms of consciousness-raising and counselling concerning the social responsibility issues.

For each question a qualitative evaluation is given by the company with a scoring system between -2 and +2.

2	Ideal performance
1	Progress beyond compliance
0	Compliance with local laws
-1	Non-compliant situation, improving
-2	No data, or No-compliant situation

Figure 44: Grid of evaluation

The stakeholders are allocated to different steps of the life cycle of the product.

Figure 45: Weighing factors of stakeholders attribution along the life cycle

With this method it is possible to give a qualitative evaluation of the different life cycle steps of the product from a social perspective and its social performance according to the different stakeholders.

Figure 46: Qualitative S-LCA carried out for the furniture demonstrator: Business as Usual scenario

Figure 46 shows that the scenario studied already goes beyond regulation compliance for most of the life cycle steps and most of the stakeholders. Further improvement could be looked out for regarding the use of the products and their users regarding health information. Regarding employment, considering some data missing, the evaluation was conservative, therefore a result is in compliance with local laws.

Figure 47: Qualitative S-LCA carried out for the furniture demonstrator: CBM#1

In the scenario where the furniture is made of particleboard using a biobased resin, the social issues and questions addressed do not enable to reveal a significant difference with the baseline scenario.

Figure 48: Qualitative S-LCA carried out for the furniture demonstrator: CBM#2

In the case of a leasing system with a repairing service, the social performance of the product is improved regarding the use phase and the users because of complementary actions undertaken to communicate on the possibilities users have to extend the lifespan of the products.

2.6.2.6 *Conclusion*

During the project, different surveys were carried out in order to identify the stakeholders and social topics that should be considered as a priority in the furniture sector. A tool was built to evaluate the social performance of the product in relation with the engagements of the company regarding its stakeholders. Results show that even in the baseline scenario, the company already has engagements showing social responsibility beyond regulation requirements. However, the eco-design of the product and the search for new business models show that there are possibilities to improve social aspects mainly regarding users.

2.6.3 S-LCA : Construction sector

2.6.3.1 *Construction prototype*

In the construction sector the collaborative effort of Conenor and Virol (wind turbine blade recycling company) resulted in the development of a new composite material made of wind turbine blade Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) waste. This is a first time ever when GFRP-waste is being recycled and used as reinforcing material fraction in manufacturing circular thermoplastic composites. The developed material is used in the production of multi-extrusion boards, panels and decks, which offer an alternative to wooden planks and pillars in outdoor use, with the core layer containing GFRP waste and the surface layer being primary scrap and recycled material (e.g. recycled HDPE- or PP-plastic from consumer packaging). This new weather resistant composite material will be tested in various outdoor

furniture and structural construction applications, examples of which are presented below.

Figure 49: Example of multi-extrusion board with the core being coarse and cascaded material and surface primary scrap and recycled material.

Figure 50: Prototype of a shelter using Conenor's multi-extrusion boards and panels

2.6.3.2 Goal and scope of the analysis

The ECOBULK construction sector demonstrator has three key circular economy objectives (see D8.3):

- To use waste thermoset composite as a raw material in outdoor furniture applications;

- To design outdoor furniture that can be dis- and re-assembled to prolong product life; and,
- To demonstrate that the product is technically recyclable.

The reference flow for the analysis is a shelter made of composite planks produced by Conenor. The shelter was installed in the facilities of Warwick University.

2.6.3.3 System boundaries definition

In order to align S-LCA with the life cycle concept, study covers cradle-to-grave, including the premanufacturing (production of inputs), manufacturing, use and post-use (waste management) steps. Following the waste hierarchy principle, the life cycle-related loops (e.g. remanufacturing, re-use, and recycling) will be also incorporated into the assessment for the comparison reasons. Figure 51 provides the value chain configuration and system boundaries for the construction demonstrator.

Figure 51: The value chain configuration and system boundaries for the construction demonstrator

The Conenor's product lifecycle is fed by the waste (e.g. materials outflow of thermoset GFRP products, such as wind turbine blades, boats & yachts etc), as well as other (primary or secondary) raw materials. Some materials could be sourced directly from the waste owner and grinded at the Conenor's facilities, while others (GFRP from wind turbine blades) may need pre-treatment elsewhere (e.g. sorting, shredding, etc.) before they could be supplied to Conenor. Conenor develops a feedstock (agglomerates) for composite components manufacturers (e.g. extruders, injection moulders and compression moulders) through addition of other raw materials. A possible intermediary step between component manufacture and end markets is product manufacture (design and assembly with other components for final structural applications), otherwise the components could go directly

to distribution (e.g. B&Q, Kingfisher, Homebase, etc.) so that they could be assembled and installed on site either directly by the end-user (internal technicians) or contractor (external company). Following the waste hierarchy principles, the end-user may want to sell/give away/dispose (pay) the assembly either to:

- Another end-user for reuse in the same application.
- Another end-user willing to reuse/repurpose assembly/component in another applications (e.g. professionals, such as designers/architects/contractors that are looking for ways to reuse products and components in architectural/engineering projects).

The main end of life recovery strategy is mechanical recycling in the Conenor's or comparable extrusion processes, which will be demonstrated as part of the EoL strategy for the construction sector. The extruded planks and panels are made substantially of waste materials and can be recycled into new planks and panels.

It is important to note that the value chain configuration provided in Figure 51 is hypothetical considering that (1) the products and solutions proposed by Conenor (recycling and utilization of GFRP waste as reinforcing material fraction in manufacturing circular thermoplastic composites for construction sector) are new with no market uptake as so far; (2) Conenor is a R&D company only acting as OEM for the sake of the project.

2.6.3.4 *Methodology for selecting stakeholders and social issues*

The methodology is similar to the furniture sector, stakeholders and social topics considered are similar.

2.6.3.5 *Assessment*

In this section, two scenarios were taken into account: a baseline scenario where the planks at the end of life are incinerated where steel components and recycled and the rest is landfilled, and a circular scenario where the planks can be recycled in a closed loop to remanufacture planks.

The difficulty in assessing this scenario is that Conenor and is a research centre, therefore not representative of an industrial company that use the solution developed by Conenor. As a result, most evaluation are conservative, considering the social performance is compliant with regulation. For users, a specific work was carried by Warwick University to ensure the stability and safety of the shelter for users.

Figure 52: Qualitative S-LCA carried out for the construction demonstrator: reference scenario

In the circular scenario, some assumptions are to identify potential social benefits regarding the recycling of the composites planks at the end of life of the product. The improvements are related to the use and end of life phase for users and local communities, most benefits come from the substitution of incineration by recycling, offering opportunities in terms of local employment and reducing health issues that could be associated with incineration activities.

Figure 53: Qualitative S-LCA carried out for the construction demonstrator: circular scenario

2.6.3.6 Conclusion

As a conclusion, the social assessment of the system studied for the construction is more complicated since the Conenor is a research centre and so their position regarding social issues is not the same as an industrial company. However, taking into account the assumptions made, the comparison of the reference and the circular scenario show paths of progression to better take into account social issues.

3 Perception study regarding recycled materials

3.1 Literature monitoring

3.1.1 Waste generation and recycling

An estimated 2.01 billion tonnes of municipal solid waste were generated in the world in 2016, and this number is expected to grow to 3.40 billion tonnes by 2050 under a business-as-usual scenario (source: What a waste 2.0, World Bank group, 2018). Rich countries have only 16% of the world's population but produce more than a third (34%) of the world's waste.

Figure 54: Projected waste generation by 2050 (Source : Data from What a waste 2.0, The World Bank group, 2018)

In comparison, **the European Union generated 2 538 million tonnes of total waste in 2016** which is 4% more than in 2008.

Figure 55: Generation of waste in Europe-28 (source: data from Eurostat)

Figure 56: Generation of waste by waste category (source: data from Eurostat, [env_wasgen])

In 2016, **wood and plastics waste represented a total 73 millions tonnes**, i.e. 3% of all the waste generated in the European Union in 2016.

In Europe again, the recycling rate of municipal waste is steadily growing with an estimated rate of **47% in 2018** (source: Eurostat).

Figure 57: Recycling rate in European Union – 28 countries (source: Data from Eurostat)

But the recycling rates can be quite different according to different flows of waste, construction and demolition waste achieving a 89% recycling rate in 2016 whereas the rate is at 41% for plastic packaging.

Figure 58: Recycling rates of different waste streams (source: Eurostat)

Nevertheless, **only 12% of material resources used in the EU in 2016 came from recycled products** and recovered materials according to the indicator called circular material use rate. It measures the contribution of recycled materials to overall demand.

Figure 59: Circular material use rate, in percentage (%), EU-28 (source: Eurostat)

The BIOREG project funded by H2020 estimated that **49% of wood waste generated in Europe is recycled in 2016** and the Eurostat statistics give a rate of **42% of recycling for plastic packaging**.

Figure 60: Wood Waste treatment in EU-28 (Source: Bioreg, 2018)

Figure 61: Recycling rate of plastic packaging waste in the EU (source: Eurostat)

Regarding some recycled materials under development in the ECOBULK project:

- In 2016, wood and plastic represented 3% of the waste generated in Europe, and
- It is considered that 49% of wood and 42% of plastic was recycled.

Key figures

Figure 62: Key figures of waste generated and recycled in Europe – 28 in 2016

3.1.2 Public perception regarding the use of recycled materials

In a recent French study (Record, R013)⁹ different brakes on the use of recycled plastics were identified from the industrial perspective. The main brakes were related to issues such as availability and technical problems (quality, homogeneity) rather than to acceptance problems, except for contact applications (food, cosmetic products).

Regarding consumers though, the report that the European Commission released in 2014 regarding "Attitudes of Europeans towards waste management and resource efficiency"¹⁰ gives some additional information. During the investigation, respondents were asked which factors they consider most important when buying a durable product. To the question "Which of the following aspects do you consider most important when buying a durable product, like a washing machine or a fridge?", **17% answered that it is important that the product is made from recycled materials.** The answer varies according to the country of the respondent, as in Spain (25%) a quarter of respondents say it is important for the product to be made from recycled materials, whereas only 5% of respondents in Estonia and Latvia regard this as an important factor when buying a durable product.

Even if some studies reveal that knowing that a brand uses recycled materials (for packaging) in its products would give a better image of the brand¹¹, it

⁹ RECORD, Perception et comportement des entreprises vis-à-vis des matières et produits recyclés, 2013, 51 p, n°11-0718/1A

¹⁰ Flash Eurobarometer 388 "Attitudes of Europeans towards Waste Management and Resource Efficiency", 2014

¹¹ ECO-EMBALLAGES, ADEME. Etude de la perception de l'emballage et d'image du recyclé, 2014, 12 pages

also seems that consumers can quickly have a lack of understanding of what “recycled” means.

In 2015, an American study (FTC and USDA)¹² examined the consumer understanding of “recycled content” and “organic” claims. 90% of consumers surveyed are confident that they have at least some understanding of what an unqualified recycled content claim means. This proportion decreases significantly with the “Pre-Consumer” and “Post-Industrial” qualified claims, with respectively 61% and 53% of answers.

3.2 Consumers perception regarding recycled materials: survey among consumers

An online survey was carried out to get a first feedback of the perception of a consumer regarding recycled materials used in final products.

The survey was elaborated in February / March 2020 and was released on the 4th April 2020 and was open until the 10th of November 2020. It is important to note that this period coincides with lockdowns in most European countries due the coronavirus crisis and that the consumers’ answers may have been biased by this situation.

The survey was spread through the social media of the project ECOBULK and spread by the ECOBULK partners. The results are being analysed. 1017 answers were collected in 20 European countries. But answers from France, Spain and Germany represent more than 80% of the answers. And 80% of the answers were collected during the first fortnight after the launch of the survey. Nevertheless, the partners asked in June to maintain the survey open in order to disseminate the existence of this survey in the media.

3.2.1 Profile of respondents

Respondents come from 21 European countries, France, Spain and Germany representing 82% of the total answers although the population of these 3 countries represent 35% of the European population of the 21 countries.

¹² FTC, USDA, Consumer Perception of “Recycled Content” and “Organic” Claims, 2056. 54p.

Figure 63: **Number of respondents per country**

Male respondents score 48% of the answers and Female represent 52% of the answers, which is consistent with the share of women in the EU population (51% in 2019¹³).

Figure 64: Distribution of gender in the top 3 countries representing 82% of the answers

The pyramid of ages of the respondents shows that one 36% of the respondents are aged between 15 and 24, which is much higher than the [17.2% share](#)¹⁴ of the European population in 2017.

¹³ <https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do>

¹⁴ Source : INSEE

Figure 65: Distribution of respondents according to their age

3.2.2 Two main key indicators

To the question “If a product contains recycled content, does it prevent you from buying it?”, 94% of the respondents answer “No”. The proportion is the same for men and women (92% for men and 93% for women). The other important output of the survey is that 85% of the respondents believe that the use of recycled materials in a product gives a better image of the brand.

Figure 66: Main key indicators of the survey

3.2.3 Other outputs of the survey

A series of seven question plus one additional question specific to the furniture was addressed to the respondents.

3.2.3.1 Concern about different issues

To the question “Indicate how concerned you are regarding each of the following issues”, 6 options of answers were given from “Not at all concerned” to “extremely concerned” (and “No opinion”).

For all the following issues, the level “very” and “extremely” concerned answers is over 50%. This rate rises to more than 80% for environmental issues: waste disposal, water and air pollution, and climate change. The issue the concerns the least the respondents is Human population growth (57%).

There is no significant differences between Male and Female answers. On the contrary the age seem to be an influencing parameter.

Figure 67: Answers to the questions "Indicate how concerned you are regarding each of the following issues" (focus on 2 top answers)

Figure 68: Differences according to the age of respondents

Male

Female

Figure 69: Differences according to gender

3.2.3.2 Main concerns by country

The eight countries presented in Figure 70, represent more than 80% of the total number of respondents to the survey.

It is the United Kingdom and in Portugal that the most respondents feel “extremely concerned” by climate change (respectively 79% and 78%), whereas it is in Turkey that this rate is the lowest (33%). Water and air pollution appear to be the second main topic of concern with a maximum of 74% for water pollutions and 67% for air pollution in Portugal. Finally, waste concern seems to be the fourth with a maximum of 61% of “extremely concerned” respondents in the UK and a minimum of 29% in Germany.

Figure 70: Proportion of “extremely concerned” in 8 European countries

Age: 15-24

Age: 25-39

Age: 40-54

Age: 55+

Figure 71: Proportion of "extremely concerned" in 8 European countries - Differences according to the age of respondents

Male

Female

Figure 72: Proportion of "extremely concerned" in 8 European countries Differences according to the gender

3.2.3.3 Waste generation perception

Respondents were then asked to express their feeling whether too much waste is generated and if they consider they make efforts to reduce their amount of household waste.

If a majority of respondents have the feeling that their country generates too much waste (67% totally agree and 95% totally and tend to agree), they also consider for 44% of them that they already make efforts to reduce waste

generation in their household and are only 20% to totally agree that their household generates too much waste.

Figure 73: Waste generation perception

Age: 15-24

Age: 25-39

Age: 40-54

Age: 55+

Figure 74: Waste generation perception- Differences according to the age of respondents

Male

Female

Figure 75: Waste generation perception- Differences according to the age of respondents

3.2.3.4 Most important materials to be recycled

Three categories of waste appear to be the most important to recycle: hard and soft plastics, aluminium. When taking into account the responses “extremely important” and “very important” the top three categories are hard and soft plastics, and glass. 78% of respondents consider wood waste are extremely of very important to recycle.

Figure 76: Top 3 most important materials to recycle: hard and soft plastics, and aluminium

Figure 77: Top 3 most important materials to recycle - Differences according to the age of respondents

Male

Female

Figure 78: Top 3 most important materials to recycle - Differences according to the age of respondents

3.2.3.5 Important parameters when purchasing a good

The three “extremely important” parameters taken into account when purchasing a production would be:

- The durability (product usable for a long time): 56%
- The product is environmentally friendly: 54%
- The product can be recycled after its use: 44%

When adding the “extremely” and “very” important answers, the three main parameters remain the same:

- The durability (product usable for a long time): 93%
- The product is environmentally friendly: 88%
- The product can be recycled after its use: 90%

Figure 79: Criteria when purchasing a product

Figure 80: Criteria when purchasing a product - Differences according to the age of respondents

Male

Female

Figure 81: Criteria when purchasing a product - Differences according to the age of respondents

3.2.3.6 Knowing that a product contains recycled materials

To the question "Which product categories would you be most likely to buy knowing that they contain recycled materials?", furniture items arrive first, followed by game / toys and then electronic goods. But when you consider the proposition of "very likely" and "extremely likely" answers, the top three categories are:

- Furniture: 84%
- Game/toys: 73%
- Small and large appliances: 74%

Figure 82: Categories of products for which the information of recycled content is expected before purchasing

Figure 83: Categories of products for which the information of recycled content is expected before purchasing - Differences according to the age of respondents

Figure 84: Categories of products for which the information of recycled content is expected before purchasing - Differences according to the age of respondents

For furniture products, the information of recycled content is the most important for storing items and tables. On the contrary, bedding products is the category for which the information is the least likely to motivate a purchase.

Figure 85: Focus on furniture items

Figure 86: Focus on furniture items - Differences according to the age of respondents

Figure 87: Focus on furniture items - Differences according to the gender of respondents

Figure 88: Focus on furniture items (details)

3.3 Sensory study on recycled material developed in ECOBULK

3.3.1 Objective of the experiment

The use of recycled material within a circular economy strategy has different challenges to face. Some of them are technical like the quality of the recycled materials, or securing supplies. But there also brakes to be lifted regarding the consumer’s behaviour towards recycled materials and the perception, positive or negative that he has about these materials.

The aim of this task in the project is to identify how the consumer perceives recycled materials which are being developed for different prototypes.

Three materials were targeted:

- A composite developed by CONENOR
- A wood particle board made with recycled particles of wood
- A non-woven material made from polyester fibers by NTT

Due to the COVID crisis, it was not possible in 2020 to receive any samples of particleboards from KEAS (Turkey). Therefore samples from anonymous manufacturers were used for the purpose of the experiment.

Composite (CONENOR)

Non-woven (NTT)

Particleboard

Figure 89: Illustration of recycled materials developed within ECOBULK

The experiment consisted in showing to a panel of naive consumers some different samples of the recycled materials developed within ECOBULK.

A protocol was defined in order to be able to assess the impact of the recycled content of the material on the sensorial perception of the material.

3.3.2 Groups of individuals

This experiment was carried out with two groups:

- Group 1: the subjects do not know the composition of the samples evaluated.
- Group 2: the subjects know from the beginning of the experiment that the samples presented are made of recycled materials.

Figure 90: Characteristics of the people involved in the experiment

3.3.3 Experiment on samples of composites from CONENOR

Four samples were used with different recycled content: wood chips, wind turbine blades, virgin and recycled HDPE among others

Figure 91: Samples of composites from CONENOR

3.3.3.1 Visual perception

The first question was related to the visual perception of the four samples: "Do you like the visual aspect of this product?"

The answers can be significantly different between the two groups:

- Group 1 find the samples visually pleasant for 50%, 40%, 35% et 45% of the people
- Group 2 find the samples visually pleasant for 50%, 17%, 17%, 44% of the people

Do you like the visual aspect of this product ?

Visual perception - Composite
Yellow sample

For the yellow sample, the most common comments are :

- Marbled appearance
- Touch of colour
- Texture
- Clean look
- Fake look

Visual perception - Composite
Blue sample

For the blue sample the most common comments are :

- Unattractive colour
- Unattractive without coating
- Uniform surface too many impurities

Do you like the visual aspect of this product ?

For the green sample the most common comments are :

- Marbled appearance
- Touch of colour
- Texture
- Modern appearance
- Unattractive without coating
- Fake look

For the pink sample, the most common comments are :

- Marbled appearance
- Clean
- Solid colour
- Unattractive without coating

Figure 92: Answers to the question: Do you like the visual aspect of this product?

We can see that the pink sample and the yellow have the most positive responses to the visual aspect for both groups.

3.3.3.2 Visual perception - composition

The second question was « In your opinion, these samples consist of : »

In your opinion, these samples consist of :

What guided your response?

Mixed materials, heterogeneous colours and particle sizes, texture, slice appearance, compressed ensemble, non-uniform colour scratches, wood debris on the slice.

Figure 93: Opinion about the composition of the material

For the group 1, who does not know that samples have recycled content, there are much more "don't know" answers than in the group 2, who gives more "Mix of virgin and recycle raw materials" answers.

For the blue sample, there is a significant different between the two groups, the second one believing it is made of a mix of raw and recycled materials, whereas group 1 has more balanced answers.

We also notice that the pink and blue samples, because of their smooth visual aspect without too many apparent stains, there are more people who consider that it is made of a mix of raw or recycled materials.

3.3.3.3 Visual perception – quality

The third question of the experiment was “How do you rate the quality of this material?”.

How do you rate the quality of this material ?

What guided your answer?

Sound of the material, visual appearance, feel, visible particles on the edge, visual (clear looks less solid), damaged edges. Quality may vary according to use.

Figure 94: Answer to the question: How do you rate the quality of this material

We can see that more people in group 2 perceive the blue, green and yellow sample as having a poor quality in contrast to group 1 where the responses for poor quality are lower. We also notice that group 2 has more "I don't know" answers than group 1.

Finally, we observe that group 1 considers the blue, green and pink samples to be of very good quality, whereas group 2 considers only the pink sample to be of very good quality.

3.3.3.4 Olfactory perception

Both groups identify a smell in the samples. Group 1 finds that in general the samples have a pleasant smell, no particular smell for the blue and pink sample. Group 2 also found the samples to have a pleasant smell, no particular smell for the blue, yellow and pink sample. In contrast to group 1,

we have more people in group 2 who do not find the smell of the 4 samples pleasant.

Figure 95 : Answer to the question: Do the samples have a smell

Both groups agree that the smell is pleasant or neither pleasant or unpleasant. However, in group 2 there are a few responses that indicate that all 4 samples have a not pleasant smell, in contrast to group 1 where there is only one response that indicates that the yellow sample has a not pleasant smell.

3.3.3.5 Tactile perception

For this question, the users evaluate the 4 samples at the same time and not separately.

It can be seen that the two groups are almost in agreement in their choice but differ in the aesthetic criterion. Group 1 is less convinced than group 2.

For all these materials, the material to the touch is :

Figure 96: Evaluation of the tactile perception

3.3.3.6 Intention to buy

We notice that group 1 has more responses of probability of purchase of product containing recycled material than group 2. We notice that the furniture where the probability of purchase decreases is for indoor products such as a shelf, a desk, a chair, a dining table and storage furniture. It is interesting to note that even outdoor items such as a garden shed or chair/bench are not considered by Group 2 users.

Would you be likely to buy the following products knowing that these composite boards contain recycled material ?

Figure 97: Answers to the question: Would you be likely to buy the following products knowing that these particle boards contain recycled materials?

3.3.3.7 Order of preference

For group 1 the pink sample comes first followed by green, yellow and finally blue.

For group 2 the pink sample is the favourite, followed by yellow, blue and finally green.

Rank these samples in order of preference: (1 being the most preferred to 4 the least preferred)

Figure 98: Rank of the samples in order of preference

Both groups place the blue sample in fourth position, where the wood particle marks are not as well integrated into the material as in the pink sample, which is in first position.

We can add that the aesthetic aspect of the material is an important point in the preferences made by group 2. In fact, in positions 1 and 2, we find the pink sample followed by green and yellow for which the surface is not as homogeneous as the pink sample.

3.3.4 Experiment on samples of nonwoven materials from NTT

Four non-woven fabric samples provided by NTT were used for the experiment, all of them containing recycled fibres.

Figure 99: Samples of composites from Conenor

3.3.4.1 Visual perception

Do you like the visual aspect of this product ?

Visual perception - Nonwoven
Pink sample

For the pink sample, the most common comments are :

- o Surface fibre appearance
- o Texture
- o Appears stiff

Visual perception - Nonwoven
Green sample

For the green sample, the most common comments are :

- o Soft and fluffy appearance
- o Seems comfortable
- o Seems pleasant
- o Airy texture

Do you like the visual aspect of this product ?

Visual perception - Nonwoven
Yellow sample

For the yellow sample, the most common comments are :

- o Marbled appearance
- o Seems comfortable
- o Thick
- o Airy appearance
- o Seems soft

Visual perception - Nonwoven
Blue sample

For the blue sample the most common comments are :

- o Unattractive colour
- o Dusty surface
- o Homogeneous
- o Pleasant texture
- o Stiff appearance
- o Good thickness

Figure 100: Answers to the question: Do you like the visual aspect of this product?

We can see that for the group 1 the green sample are most appreciate. For group 2 is the blue sample that is most appreciated.

3.3.4.2 Visual perception - composition

What guided your answer?
 Hardness of the samples (blue and pink), presence of coloured elements, texture, density, different textures, appearance of the material, thickness of the layers, shiny filaments (looks artificial).

Figure 101: Opinion about the composition of the material

For both groups, and especially for this kind of subject, it seems to be more difficult to determine the subject. The graph shows a lot of "don't know" answers for both groups. However, it can be seen that group 1 identifies the green, yellow and pink samples as having raw materials, whereas group 2 goes for a mix of materials (recycled and raw materials).

3.3.4.3 Visual perception - quality

What guided your answer?
 Density of the material, resistance of the foam to a compressive force, height, texture, weight. The quality will also depend on the function of the material.

Figure 102: Answer to the question: How do you rate the quality of this material

It is complicated to evaluate the material alone without having the finished product and knowing the final use of the object, hence the number of "I don't know" answers in group 1. Indeed, we notice that for both groups the blue sample (which is the hardest) is considered qualitative compared to the green and pink sample (softer) considered non-qualitative by some users.

3.3.4.4 *Olfactory perception*

Both groups identify an odour in the samples.

Group 1 does not identify any particular odour in the samples except for the yellow sample.

For group 2 the users notice an odour. The results are divided between those who like the smell and those who have no positive or negative judgement about the smell.

Figure 103 : Answer to the question: Do the samples have a smell

3.3.4.5 *Tactile perception*

For this question, users first evaluate 2 samples (pink and blue) at the same time and then 2 other samples (yellow and green).

For group 1, the pink and blue samples are perceived to be cheaper than the yellow and green samples which are perceived to be more luxurious.

For all these materials, the touch of the material is :

Figure 104: Evaluation of the tactile perception

For this question, users first evaluate 2 samples (pink and blue) at the same time and then 2 other samples (yellow and green).

For group 2, the pink and blue samples are perceived as slightly less comfortable than the yellow and green samples. The blue and pink samples have a rougher surface than the yellow and green samples. In terms of elasticity, the pink and blue samples are perceived as less elastic than the green and yellow samples.

For all these materials, the material to the touch is :

Figure 105: Evaluation of the tactile perception

3.3.4.6 Intention to buy

For the group 1, for all 4 samples users are less likely to buy a mattress or a sofa. For the pink and blue samples there is also a reluctance to buy products such as a duvet or a pillow/cushion.

For the group 2, for the yellow and green samples users are less likely to buy a mattress, sofa or chair. Conversely, for products such as a duvet and a

pillow/pillow the probability is high. For the pink and blue samples there is a high probability of buying sofas, mattresses and chairs.

Unlike other products such as duvets and pillows/pillows where the likelihood is almost non-existent.

Would you be likely to buy the following products made from recycled materials ?

Would you be likely to buy the following products made from recycled materials ?

Figure 106: Answers to the question: Would you be likely to buy the following products knowing that these particle boards contain recycled materials?

3.3.4.7 Order of preference

For group 1 the yellow sample comes first followed by the green sample, the blue and finally the pink.

For group 2 the blue sample is the favourite, followed by pink, green and yellow are tied in third place.

Rank these samples in order of preference: (1 being the most preferred to 4 the least preferred)

Figure 107: Rank of the samples in order of preference

3.3.5 Experiment on samples of particleboards

Four samples particleboards with recycled content were used

Figure 108: Samples of particleboard

3.3.5.1 Visual perception

Do you like the visual aspect of this product ?

Visual perception - Particleboard Blue sample

For the blue sample, the most common comments are:

- Texture
- Colour
- Visible particles
- impression of solidity
- Original
- Not aesthetic without coating

Visual perception - Particleboard Green sample

For the green sample, the most common comments are:

- Texture
- Colour
- Fine particles
- Simple
- Seems less solid
- Not aesthetic without coating

Do you like the visual aspect of this product ?

Visual perception - Particleboard Yellow sample

For the yellow sample, the most common comments are:

- Texture
- Colour
- Visible particles
- impression of solidity
- Soft to the touch
- Not aesthetic without coating
- Good apparent quality

Visual perception - Particleboard Pink sample

For the pink sample, the most common comments are:

- Texture
- Fine finish to avoid the appearance of chipboard
- Simple
- Not aesthetic without coating

We can see that the pink sample has the most positive responses to the visual aspect for both groups, as well as the blue sample.

Figure 109: Answers to the question: Do you like the visual aspect of this product?

3.3.5.2 Visual perception - composition

In your opinion, these samples consist of :

What guided your answer?
The appearance of the blue particles on the edge, the visual aspect, the size of the fibres, the texture and the weight.

Figure 110: Opinion about the composition of the material

We can notice that group 1 for the yellow sample has more answers indicating that the material is only recycled while group 2 aims more at a mixture of materials (recycled and virgin).

3.3.5.3 Visual perception - quality

How do you rate the quality of this material ?

What guided your answer?
The sound of the material, the presence of blue particles (brings a doubt on the quality), crumbling edge, the quality seems good depending on the uses, the weight, difficult to test the quality just at the visual level.

Figure 111: Answer to the question: How do you rate the quality of this material

We note that in general the 4 samples are rated as being of good quality for both groups. Some people in group 1 found the blue sample to be of very good quality. In group 2 the green sample is rated as poor quality.

3.3.5.4 Olfactory perception

Both groups identify an odour in the samples. Group 1 recognises an unpleasant odour in all 4 samples, whereas Group 2 does not make a remark for any of the 4 samples.

The smell is well identified by the testers but the smell is not a positive or negative element, even if group 1 has more answers that the samples have a pleasant smell compared to group 2.

Figure 112 : Answer to the question: Do the samples have a smell

3.3.5.5 Tactile perception

For this question the users evaluate the 4 samples at the same time and not separately.

Group 2 (knowing from the beginning that the material is recycled) has a higher number of answers for the low environmental impact of the material than group 1. The same applies to the high environmental impact, which is higher for group 1 than for group 2.

For all these materials, the material to the touch is :

Figure 113: Evaluation of the tactile perception

3.3.5.6 Intention to buy

Would you be likely to buy the following products knowing that these particleboards contain recycled material ?

Figure 114: Answers to the question: Would you be likely to buy the following products knowing that these particle boards contain recycled materials?

We note that in both groups the users would be willing to buy products containing recycled material. However, we can also note that in group 2 there are some people who would not buy products (desk, coffee table, dining table, bed base) containing recycled material.

3.3.5.7 Order of preference

Rank these samples in order of preference: (1 being the most preferred to 4 the least preferred)

Figure 115: Rank of the samples in order of preference

For group 1 the blue and pink samples seem to be the most preferred, with the green sample coming in third and the yellow sample in last place.

For group 2, the pink sample comes first followed by the yellow sample, with blue and green in last place.

3.3.6 Transversal question about social conditions of production

For this question the majority of testers answered that they did not know about the social conditions under which the products are manufactured.

A minority of group 1 think that the particleboard and non-woven samples are manufactured under socially responsible conditions. For Group 2 it is noted that for some of the respondents the particleboard samples and composites are produced under responsible conditions.

Do you think that these materials are produced under socially responsible conditions ?

Figure 116: Answer to the question: do you think that these materials are produced under socially responsible conditions?

3.3.7 Conclusions of the experiments on samples of materials

This experiment through the senses (touch, sight and smell) allowed us to observe that the users' visual approach takes the upper hand when appreciating and choosing materials, for questions such as quality or when making a purchase. The visual aspect remains the first determining element, followed by the sense of touch and finally the sense of smell.

The use that the object will have is also a determining point in the choice of the material, which allows a choice to be made in terms of quality, thickness, colour, among other elements that users identified during the tests.

The information revealed to Group 2 did not seem to have much influence because the visual aspect of the material (colour, texture among others) revealed the recycled side of it. Nevertheless, we could notice that when it

comes to buying furniture, group 2 is less inclined to buy indoor furniture than outdoor furniture.

We can conclude that the aspect of the material does indeed have an influence on the choice of the users, but it is not a determining factor and that the use completes the choice for one material than another.

4 User survey for the construction demonstrator

During the last year of the project, once the shelter was installed in the facilities of Coventry, an online survey was carried out. It was not possible to analyse the results therefore, some of the raw results are presented in the appendix.

5 Conclusion

Regarding social aspects, many different activities were carried out within the ECOBULK project, the aim of them being to identify links between new circular business models and social issues.

Social assessment of the products conducted, showed that for the:

- Automotive demonstrator: the differences between the systems studied are quite low because of the origin of materials used in the project and the pre-industrial scale of the experiments, meaning there would be some optimization at an industrial scale. On the contrary, simulation involving significantly different sourcing of the raws materials show important social differences between the scenarios
- Furniture demonstrator: for this sector, some potential benefits are related to the users by facilitating the extension of the lifespan of the furniture sector
- Construction demonstrator: a lot of assumptions were made given that the evaluation is not carried out at the level of an industrial company. However, the assessment shows that recycling at the end of life instead of incinerating planks could lead to social benefits for users and local communities.

In parallel of the assessment of the products, different surveys and experiments were carried out. The general results are that people show a great interest in promoting recycling, and the use of recycled materials. However, there are issues about communicating on the recycled content of a product and the perception of the consumers regarding the use of products containing recycled content.

6 References

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7 Appendix I: Weighting factors used in the study. S-LCIA method: Social Hotspot 2019 Subcat & Cat Method w Damages

Impact category [weighting factor, WF]	Subcategory [weighting factor, WF]	Social indicator	Weighting factors (in Mrheq/worker-hour) according to risk level			
			VH	HR	MR	LR
1) Labour rights & decent work [WF = 1]	1A) Wage [WF = 1.818]	Risk that avg. wage is below country minimum wage	13.333	6.667	1.333	0.133
		Risk that sector avg. wage is below living wage	13.333	6.667	1.333	0.133
		Risk that sector avg. wage is below sweatfree wage	13.333	6.667	1.333	0.133
	1B) Poverty [WF = 1.818]	Percent of population living under the relevant poverty line	40	20	4	0.4
	1D) Child labour [WF = 1.818]	Risk of child labour by sector (qualitative)	40	20	4	0.4
	1E) Forced labour [WF = 1.818]	Overall forced labour in country	40	20	4	0.4
	1F) Excessive working time [WF = 1.818]	Percent of population working > 60 hrs per week	40	20	4	0.4
	1G) Freedom of association [WF = 1.818]	Overall risk of freedom of association	40	20	4	0.4
	1H) Migrant labour [WF = 1.818]	Evidence of risk to migrant workers (qualitative)	40	20	4	0.4
	1I) Social benefits [WF = 1.818]	Overall risk of inadequate social benefits	40	20	4	0.4
	1J) Labour laws & conventions [WF = 1.818]	Number of labour laws by sector	40	20	4	0.4

Impact category [weighting factor, WF]	Subcategory [weighting factor, WF]	Social indicator	Weighting factors (in Mrheq/worker-hour) according to risk level			
			VH	HR	MR	LR
	1K) Discrimination [WF = 1.818]	Prevalence of discrimination in the workplace (qualitative)	40	20	4	0.4
	1L) Unemployment [WF = 1.818]	Unemployment percentage at sector level	40	20	4	0.4
2 Health & safety [WF = 1]	2A) Occupational toxics & hazards [WF = 10]	Disability-adjusted life years due to occupational-related lung cancer	13.333	6.667	1.333	0.133
		Overall occupational cancer risk - loss of life (DALYs)	13.333	6.667	1.333	0.133
		Overall occupational noise exposure risk	13.333	6.667	1.333	0.133
	2B) Injuries & fatalities [WF = 10]	Fatal injuries by sector	20	10	2	0.2
		Non-fatal work related injuries by sector	20	10	2	0.2
3) Human rights [WF = 1]	3A) Indigenous rights [WF = 4]	Indigenous sector issues identified	20	10	2	0.2
		Overall risk of indigenous rights being infringed	20	10	2	0.2
	3B) Gender equity [WF = 4]	Overall gender inequity in country	40	20	4	0.4
	3C) High conflict zones [WF = 4]	Overall high conflict	40	20	4	0.4
	3D) Non-communicable diseases [WF = 4]	Overall non-communicable diseases and other health risks	40	20	4	0.4
	3E) Communicable diseases [WF = 4]	Age-standardized MRs from com. diseases (per 100,000 population)	8	4	0.8	0.08
		Cases of HIV (per 1000 adults 15-49 years)	8	4	0.8	0.08
		Cases of tuberculosis (per 100,000 population)	8	4	0.8	0.08
		Dengue fever, incidence rate (per 100,000 population)	8	4	0.8	0.08
Notified cases of Malaria (per 100,000 population)		8	4	0.8	0.08	

Impact category [weighting factor, WF]	Subcategory [weighting factor, WF]	Social indicator	Weighting factors (in Mrheq/worker-hour) according to risk level				
			VH	HR	MR	LR	
4) Governance [WF = 1]	4A) Legal system [WF = 10]	Overall fragility in legal system	40	20	4	0.4	
	4B) Corruption [WF = 10]	Overall corruption	40	20	4	0.4	
5) Community [WF = 1]	5A) Access to drinking water [WF = 4]	% total access to an improved source of drinking water	40	20	4	0.4	
	5B) Access to sanitation [WF = 4]	% total access to an improved source of sanitation	40	20	4	0.4	
	5C) Children out of school [WF = 4]	Percent of children out of primary school, total	40	20	4	0.4	
	5D) Access to hospital beds [WF = 4]	Number of hospital beds per 1000 population	40	20	4	0.4	
	5E) Smallholder vs commercial farms [WF = 4]		Largeholdings land % < x hectares	10	5	1	0.1
			Percentage of commercially-owned farms in country	10	5	1	0.1
			Percentage of family-owned farms in country	10	5	1	0.1
Smallholdings land % < x hectares			10	5	1	0.1	

8 Appendix I: Market prices used to develop the S-LCI

Component	Unit	Market price (EUR/unit)	Data source / Comments
Virgin ABS	kg	3.00	bvse market report: plastics, September 2021: https://plasticker.de/preise/marktbericht_en.php ABS w/b, avg. price for Jun-Ago 2021
Virgin PLA	kg	3.48	https://visionbiotech.en.made-in-china.com PLA, avg. price (3 USD/kg), as sold in made-in-china.com (date of query: 04/11/2021)
Virgin PP (or P/E)	kg	2.20	bvse market report: plastics, September 2021: https://plasticker.de/preise/marktbericht_en.php PP copolymer, avg. price for Jun-Ago 2021
Recycled ABS	kg	2.36	bvse market report: plastics, September 2021: https://plasticker.de/preise/marktbericht_en.php ABS regranolates, avg. price for Jun-Ago 2021
Recycled PP	kg	0.97	bvse market report: plastics, September 2021: https://plasticker.de/preise/marktbericht_en.php PP regranolates, avg. price for Jun-Ago 2021
Glass fibre (GF)	kg	1.68	https://porter36.en.made-in-china.com Glass fibre, chopped strands E-class for thermoplastics, avg. price (1.45 USD/kg), as sold in made-in-china.com (date of query: 04/11/2021)
Natural fibre (NF)	kg	0.91	INDEXBOX (2021). World - Jute And Jute-Like Fibers - Market Analysis, Forecast, Size, Trends and Insights Jute fibre, avg. import price 2020 (0.788 USD/kg)
Talcum (T)	kg	0.48	https://huabangmineral.en.made-in-china.com Talc powder for plastics, avg. price (0.385 USD/kg), as sold in made-in-china.com (04/11/2021)
Electricity	kWh	0.107	EUROSTAT (2021): https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Electricity_price_statistics Electricity prices for non-household consumers, first half 2021, Spain.

Component	Unit	Market price (EUR/unit)	Data source / Comments
Natural gas	m ³	0.316	EUROSTAT (2021): https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Natural_gas_price_statistics Natural gas prices for non-household consumers, first half 2021, Spain (0.0237 EUR/kWh; 13.34 kWh/m ³).
Road transport, truck	tkm (tonne-km)	0.070	Bína et al. (2014). Comparative model of unit costs of road and rail freight transport for selected European countries. <i>European Journal of Business and Social Sciences</i> , 3(4), 127-136. European avg. costs for road freight transport.
Waste paint sludge	kg	0.275	Ruffino et al. (2021). Cost analysis and environmental assessment of recycling paint sludge in asphalt pavements. <i>Environmental Science and Pollution Research</i> , 28(19), 24628-24638.
Cardboard waste	kg	0.217	Avg. industry price (130 EUR/m ³) Bulk density (600 kg/m ³) according to: IHOBE (2019). EEH AURREZTEN: Manual de la herramienta de apoyo para la redacción y revisión de EGRs, PGRs e IFGs.
Wooden packaging waste	kg	0.355	Avg. industry price (130 EUR/m ³) Bulk density (366 kg/m ³) according to: IHOBE (2019). EEH AURREZTEN: Manual de la herramienta de apoyo para la redacción y revisión de EGRs, PGRs e IFGs.
Metallic packaging waste	kg	0.130	Avg. industry price (130 EUR/m ³) Bulk density (1,000 kg/m ³) according to: IHOBE (2019). EEH AURREZTEN: Manual de la herramienta de apoyo para la redacción y revisión de EGRs, PGRs e IFGs.

9 Appendix III: Survey conducted by Coventry University

List of surveys and number of answers:

- EcoBulk User Engagement Questionnaire - CU Estates Building Surveyors (3)
- EcoBulk User Engagement Questionnaire - Students (21)
- EcoBulk User Engagement Questionnaire - CU Internal Installers (3)
- EcoBulk User Engagement Questionnaire - CU Procurement Team (1)
- EcoBulk User Engagement Questionnaire - CU Staff and Academics (13)
- EcoBulk User Engagement Questionnaire - External Procurement Team (1)
- EcoBulk User Engagement Questionnaire - Futurelets (2)

Online surveys

EcoBulk User Engagement Questionnaire - CU Estates Building Surveyors

Showing 3 of 3 responses

Showing **all** responses

Showing **all** questions

Response rate: 3%

- 1** I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Yes 3 (100%)
No | 0

- 2** I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason, without my medical, social care, education, or legal rights being affected.

Yes 3 (100%)
No | 0

- 3** I agree to take part in the above study.

Yes 3 (100%)
No | 0

Circular Economy and ECOBULK Project

- 4** What is your current role at Coventry University?

1 / 10

Showing all 2 responses	
BIM Manager	687595-687586-85759834
Electrical Engineer	687595-687586-85768506

5 How aware and concerned you are of the following issues:

5.1 Waste management/disposal

5.2 Pollution by single use plastic

5.3 Recycling of plastics

5.4 Recycling of large bulky waste (e.g. from construction)

5.5 Recycling of composite materials (glass fibre, carbon fibre, others)

5.6 Reuse and repurposing of products

Multi answer: Percentage of respondents who selected each answer option (e.g. 100% would represent that all this question's respondents chose that option)

6 For each of the following statements, select whether you strongly agree, agree, neither agree or disagree, disagree, or strongly disagree.

6.1 The UK as a whole generates too much waste

Multi answer: Percentage of respondents who selected each answer option (e.g. 100% would represent that all this question's respondents chose that option)

6.2 Your office/business is generating too much waste

Multi answer: Percentage of respondents who selected each answer option (e.g. 100% would represent that all this question's respondents chose that option)

6.3 Your office/business make efforts to reduce the amount of waste and recycle more

6.4 Your household generates too much waste

6.5 Your household make efforts to reduce the amount of waste and recycle more

7 Do you feel sustainability and energy efficiency at CU is reflected well?

8 Are you aware of the Circular Economy concept?

9 Would you like to know more about the Circular Economy concept?

10 Do you think Circular Economy is the way forward?

11 Would you find any difficulties in undertaking such approach?

11.a If Yes, please describe

No responses

12 Is the EcoBulk project beneficial and heading in a positive direction in terms of sustainability?

13 Would you like to know more about the EcoBulk project?

14 How safe is the EcoBulk products for site?

15 Does it require planning permission?

16 Does it adhere to local standards and regulations?

17 Does the product interfere significantly with the surrounding including services etc?

18 Have you ever encountered similar products?

19 Has CU considered modular construction for works on campus?

20 What is done with the waste developed from Construction projects on campus?

Showing all 2 responses	
It's disposed of by specialist removal companies.	687595-687586-85759834
Each project will be different, at very least CU will specify waste transfer notices and carrier licences. It may be worthwhile speaking to someone in our development team as they could fully answer this question.	687595-687586-85768506

21 Is there a disposal policy?

22 Is any material sent for reuse or recycling?

22.a If Yes, please expand below:

Showing 1 response	
Materials such as furniture and IT equipment are re-used. Waste is sorted and recycled. have a look at our sustainability pages https://www.coventry.ac.uk/the-university/key-information/green-campus/sustainability-involvement/	687595-687586-85768506

23 Are there demolition audits in place for internal and contractors?

23.a If Yes, please expand below:

Showing 1 response	
I do not deal with demolitions, but i am aware of the process.	687595-687586-85768506

24 Would you consider bringing in a demolition audit for future projects?

10 Appendix IV: ECOBULK General Public Survey Results & Summary (made by MICROCAB)

Author:

Microcab Industries Ltd.

Date Published:

November 2021

ECOBULK Work Package:

2.2; 7.1; 8.1

Partners Involved:

Microcab

UPC

FCBA

AIMPLAS

10.1 Summary:

As part of ECOBULK work package 2.2 Microcab designed a questionnaire to survey the general public on their concerns towards environmental factors and their understanding of the circular economy. The survey considered the participants age and environment, allowing various distinguishing points to later determine the participants values and understanding of the subjects in question. A total of 27 questions were written. The questions were written onto an online survey host website, named 'SurveyJS'.

UPC supported Microcab in this project by writing the interactive survey onto the SurveyJS website, as well as creating a product page for the Microcab VIANOVA with links to the survey through the ECOBULK 'End Users and Stakeholders Platform'. This platform allowed Microcab to further disseminate products and ECOBULK interests to a wide audience.

Platform link: <https://eushp.ecobulk.upc.edu/product?productId=VIANOVA>

The surveys were sent out as a 'friends and family' approach, where Microcab could guarantee a response from a wide and varied audience. All ECOBULK partners were also invited to share the web links to their friends and family to further the response rates. The project successfully gained 142 responses by the closing date of 26th November 2021.

10.2 Questions Asked:

About you...

Age Range

Under 18 / 18-24 / 25-34 / 35-44 / 45-54 / 55-64 / 65+

Please tick your most used modes of transport:

Walking / Self-Propelled Mobility (Bicycle, Scooter, Skateboard) / Taxi / Rideshare / Car / Bus / Tram / Train

Theories & Terminology

Had you heard of the term 'Circular Economy' before today?

Yes / No

Had you heard of the term 'Remanufacture' before today?

Yes / No

Environmental Issues

Pollution

Are you happy that diesel and petrol cars are being phased out by the government?

Yes / No

Does air quality in cities concern you?

Yes / No

How much do you feel you do to actively reduce your carbon footprint?

Not at all / Little / Somewhat / Much / A great deal

Describe your position on inner cities introducing clean air zones? Example, Birmingham Clean Air Zone

Strongly Agree / Agree / Undecided / Disagree / Strongly Disagree

Waste

How concerned are you regarding the amount of waste produced by society?

Not at all / Little / Somewhat / Much / A great deal

Do you actively seek to recycle higher value products?

Not at all / Little / Somewhat / Much / A great deal

Would you be more likely to recycle if it financially benefitted you?

Yes / No

Products

Sales

How likely are you to purchase products with 'Eco Credentials'?

Not probable / Somewhat improbable / Neutral / Somewhat probable / Very probable

Do you like to purchase products that you know are better for the environment?

Yes / No

Please rate how much consideration you place on environmental aspects of the products that you purchase:

Not at all / Little / Somewhat / Much / A great deal

Would you pay a premium to purchase or use eco products?

Yes / No

Would you purchase remanufactured products if warranted the same as new?

Yes / No

Are you interested in purchasing products that utilise 'sustainable design'?

Yes / Yes, only if price is not affected / No

What level of priority do you feel that designers should place on 'sustainable design'?

Not at all / Little / Somewhat / Much / A great deal

Please rate how important the environmental impact is to your product purchase habits:

Not at all / Little / Somewhat / Much / A great deal

Aesthetic

Do you consider products that look 'eco' to be more or less valuable?

More / No Opinion / Less

Are you more likely to purchase a product that showcases environmental benefits?

Yes / No

Do you like the 'eco' aesthetic?

Yes / No

Ownership / Sharing

Have you heard of the sharing economy, for example, Public Bike Share Schemes?

Yes / No

Have you heard of car clubs?

Yes / No

Have you ever used the product of a sharing transport scheme?

Yes / No

When was the last time that you used a shared platform for mobility?

Never / Today / Last Week / Last Month / Last Year / More than 2 years

Would you own a car if you could pay by mile to use a shared car located close by?

Yes / Reduce Use of My Vehicle / No

10.3 Results:

The document will analyse key survey answers and comment where necessary on results.

The demographics of survey responders:

Of the 140 responses, the largest age range group was 35 to 44, closely followed by the groups: 45 – 54 and 25 – 34. Only 1 respondent was aged below 18.

The majority of responders indicated 'Car' as one of their methods of transport in the multi-selection question regarding preferred method of transport. The least being 'Rideshare' with only 1 person selecting this option.

Results show that although both terms, 'Remanufacture' and 'Circular Economy' had been heard of by the respondents, 'Circular Economy' was a more recognised term.

Similarly, the majority of the answers supplied showed that the public were in favour of government intervention or support for the progression towards cleaner cities. This suggests that the sample group is overwhelmingly concerned towards having cleaner environments in the future.

The previous statement is confirmed when results show that over 80% of the responders showed a positive position towards government and council backed clean air zones in cities.

The sample group showed that, on the whole, they perceive that their actions actively reduce their carbon footprint in some way and that the level of waste produced by today's society is something that they are greatly concerned about. Only with only 0.7% of responders not showing any level of concern.

With most of the public showing concern towards environmental factors, their behaviour was also in line with their beliefs in most cases. The sample group actively seek to solve the environmental issues discussed in the previous survey questions. The next statements regard the public's behaviour.

96.5% of the sample group actively seek to recycle higher value products at end of use and more than 99% seek to purchase products that they know are better for the environment.

However, not all the group's behaviour towards recycling were because of financial reasons, suggesting other factors play a role in behaviours around recycling.

From the previous statement, it can be suggested that the purchasers of products with "eco credentials" may behave this way for more than financial benefit or place more value in these products as

they feel that this supports areas that they have expressed concern for. This statement is supported further by over 99% of responses stating a positive answer towards their preference for products that are better for the environment.

The public place "much" or "a great deal" of consideration on environmental products that they purchase. A total of 55% answered this way. With 83% stating that they would pay a premium for this.

The public's views are investigated further, when asked about designers placing value on environmental issues, 100% stated that designers at least give a little priority towards sustainability. More than 96% of responses told

the survey that they would purchase remanufactured products if warranted the same as new.

To expand insights into public views on design, more questions were asked. The following questions seek to gain further understanding for a designer to consider:

Do you consider products that look 'eco' to be more or less attractive?

Are you more likely to purchase products that showcase environmental benefits?

In these cases, the public view was only ever 7% not in favour of the statements above. Meaning that 93% of respondents consider obvious design for sustainability a valuable asset of the products they interact with or purchase.

The next section explores sharing platforms:

Only 5% of responders said that they had never heard of a sharing economy. However, a far greater amount (94 people) had never used a shared transport scheme and 27% had never heard of a "car club".

Responders told the survey that if they had access to a local shared platform, 71% suggested that they would make use of the service. However, currently only 6% of the people in this survey said

that they used a car share platform in the last week.

10.4 Results Conclusion

It is clear from the findings of this survey that the general public are not only aware of the environmental problems that we face today, but also seek to actively reduce their contributions to the problems. Their behaviour suggests a willingness to value products highly that reduce environmental harm higher than other products, in some cases, more than through cost alone. The public told that showcasing environmental issues is of importance to them and that their product purchasing habits would reflect such behaviours.

Shared mobility schemes could take advantage of a public's willingness to reduce their carbon footprint or other environmental issues. However, from the sample population that was surveyed, there was a clear lack of access to a shared transport scheme.

More could be done by educators, politicians, and company advertisers to introduce the public to Circular Economy, Remanufacturing and the benefits that can be gained from using these systems. Car sharing economies can control many aspects of the circular economy and remanufacture, using them to their advantage, this would raise the value of the products of these systems in the public's view.

10.5 Interpretation of Results

Microcab can use the findings of this survey to influence company decisions in the future. Knowing that the public has a clear desire to reduce its environmental impact, the company can design products and services to take to market that address the issues discussed in this survey. The company can actively showcase CE ready products, knowing that the products will be well received and highly valued by the customer base. Microcab can address barriers to market for car sharing economies by utilising clear design for the environment and advertising the benefits of the use of car clubs, shared mobility platforms and the use of CE ready products.